

Guide to Low Impedance Measurements using Digital Sampling Setup

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Abstract

Following document is practice guide for measurement of low impedances. In its first part it covers general problems related to the measurement of low impedances. It shows various impedance standard types, proper connections to the bridge/EIS meter and corrections that can be applied to improve uncertainty of measurement. This section of the guide has no ambition to cover entire impedance measurement problematic. It just focuses to problems that are typical for low impedances. The general problem of impedance measurement was already sufficiently described in details in guide “Impedance Measurement Handbook” [14]. Authors of this guide strongly encourages readers of this guide to read the aforementioned Keysight Handbook before continuing with following chapters.

Next part of this guide presents possibilities of arranging simple digital sampling impedance bridge setups suitable for calibration in the range of impedances and frequencies typically required for Electrolytic Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) of batteries. In particular it focuses to measurement of impedances below $1\ \Omega$ in frequency range from 0.01 Hz to 5 kHz. The setups are based on the commonly available instrumentation often present in the labs and on an open source SW tools.

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Contents

1	Low impedance measurement	2
1.1	Adapters	5
1.1.1	4TP to 2/4-wire interfacing	5
1.1.2	4-wire interfacing	6
1.1.3	4-wire to 4TP interfacing	6
1.2	Concept of SHORT correction	7
1.2.1	4-wire short	9
2	Reference impedance bridge	11
2.1	Selection of measurement topology	11
2.1.1	Guarding buffer and DC bias eliminator	16
2.2	Selection of digitizer	17
2.2.1	Keysight 3458A	17
2.2.2	National Instruments NI9238 or NI9239	19
2.3	Synchronization of DDS and digitizer	21
2.4	TWM tool as Digital Sampling Bridge	25
2.4.1	Digitizer setup	25
2.4.2	Corrections setup - mapping of channels to impedance standards	28
2.4.3	Measurement setup	29
2.4.4	Initiating measurement and troubleshooting	31
2.4.5	Viewing results	33
2.5	Open Z bridge tool	34
2.5.1	Interfacing to TWM	34
2.5.2	Configuring bridge/digitizer	35
2.5.3	Configuring source	36
2.5.4	Initiating new measurement	39
2.5.5	Viewing results	40
2.6	Setup calibration and Uncertainty of measurement	43
2.6.1	Coaxial network contribution	43
2.6.2	Digitizer uncertainty contribution	44
2.6.3	Basic calibration via Open Z bridge	45
2.6.4	Calibration of linearity	50
2.6.5	Calibration of input impedance	52
2.6.6	Calibration timebase frequency	54

1 Low impedance measurement

Electrical impedance measurement is, in principle, an extension of DC resistance measurement by using alternating current (AC) instead of direct current (DC). The use of AC current conveniently eliminates one problem common for many DC measurements, the thermoelectric effects. As the polarity of the excitation current and measured voltage drop alternates, the offsets caused by the thermal voltages are subtracted for each period of the AC signal. On the other hand, the use of AC current brings a lot of another complications which makes AC impedance metrology quite challenging. First and fundamental difference is the DC resistance R_{DC} (real number) becomes a complex impedance \hat{Z} , which has its magnitude $|Z|$ and phase angle ϕ (polar form) or real and imaginary components R_S and X_S (Cartesian form):

$$\hat{Z}_X = \frac{\hat{U}_X}{\hat{I}_X} = R_S + jX_S = |Z| \cdot e^{j\phi}, \quad (1)$$

where \hat{U}_X is measured voltage drop and \hat{I}_X is current via the impedance \hat{Z} according Fig. 1. The common problem with the DC measurement is measurement offset due to series impedance (resistance) of terminals. The left circuit in Fig. 1 shows simple two terminal connection (2T), where the measured voltage drop \hat{U}_X is increased by the voltage drops on the terminals impedances \hat{Z}_{CH} and \hat{Z}_{CL} . Such connection is sufficient only for high impedances, where the terminals have negligible impedance compared to the measured impedance \hat{Z} . For low impedances, the four terminal connection (4T) is used, same as in case of DC resistance metering. If the sensing current via the series impedances \hat{Z}_{PH} and \hat{Z}_{PL} of potential terminals is negligible, the effect of the current terminals impedance is suppressed.

Figure 1: Basic types of DC resistance and impedance measurements. Left: 2-terminal (2T), Middle: 4-terminal connection (4T), Right: Mutual coupling problem for 4T measurements.

However, 4T measurement is the point where DC resistance and impedance metrology starts to diverge. Whereas for DC resistance the only condition for accurate measurement is low (ideally zero) current leakage via the potential terminals H_{POT} - L_{POT} , in case of impedance it is also necessary to take into account mutual couplings (mutual inductance) between the particular terminals, namely between current and potential ones as is illustrated in Fig. 1 on the right.

The mutual inductance M between the current lead H_{CUR} and potential lead H_{POT} will result in apparent series reactance of the 4T measurement:

$$X_M = \omega \cdot M, \quad (2)$$

where ω is angular frequency of the measurement. When measuring pure resistance R , the mutual inductance will result in apparent shift in measured time constant τ of the impedance:

$$\Delta\tau = \frac{M}{R}. \quad (3)$$

Alternatively, angular error of the impedance \hat{Z} measurement can be expressed:

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{M}{R} \cdot \omega. \quad (4)$$

Assuming example of measured impedance of $1\ \Omega$ (pure resistive), frequency of $1\ \text{kHz}$ and mutual coupling just $20\ \text{nH}$, which is very optimistic estimate of non-coaxial leads connection, the apparent reactance will be $125\ \mu\Omega$ and thus angular error of measurement will be roughly 7° .

Apparently, even small coupling can cause significant errors of measurement. Although this effect can be suppressed by performing so called SHORT correction, the geometrical repeatability of the leads connection to the measured impedance will be limiting factor of measurement accuracy. Therefore, in impedance metrology, classical 4T measurement of low impedances is not preferred. Instead, the four terminal-pair (4TP) connection was introduced. The principle is shown in Fig. 2. In 4TP connection, the

Figure 2: Four terminal (left) vs. four terminal-pair connection (right) measurement of 4TP impedance standard.

measurement current \hat{I}_X is sent through the impedance standard \hat{Z}_X and the current then returns back to the source through to coaxial shield as shown in the Fig. 2. The shield is usually grounded to the fifth terminal of the bridge, which is measurement ground or guard, hence such connection is sometimes called five-terminal (5T). This arrangement partially reduces effective inductance of the standard due to mutual coupling between the shield and internal impedance element and connection, but mainly, if properly mechanically designed, it reduces magnetic radiation of the current cables. The current via the impedance \hat{Z}_X is opposite to the current via the shield, so their magnetic fields subtract and mostly eliminate each other. Therefore, even if there is mutual coupling between the potential and current cables, the effect is greatly reduced. This is of course truth only for the coupling between the cables, but internal structure of the standard has finite dimensions, so residual magnetic radiation will be always present, but still reduced.

Figure 3: Illustration of shield impedance of 4TP standard.

However, another problem arises from the nature of 4TP standard. True 4TP measurement of impedance is defined as follows:

$$\hat{Z}_{\text{EF}} = \frac{\hat{U}_{\text{PH}} - \hat{U}_{\text{PL}}}{\hat{I}_X}, \quad (5)$$

where \hat{U}_{PH} and \hat{U}_{PL} are port voltages shown in Fig. 2 on the right and \hat{I}_X is current via the standard. Therefore, if there is impedance of the standard's shield \hat{Z}_G between the ports H_{POT} and L_{POT} as shown

in Fig. 3, it will inevitably become part of the measured effective impedance of the standard:

$$\hat{Z}_{\text{EF}} = \frac{\hat{U}_{\text{PH}} - \hat{U}_{\text{PL}}}{I_{\text{X}}} = \hat{Z} + \hat{Z}_{\text{G}}. \quad (6)$$

This shield impedance is present for all the standards having e.g. four BNC ports placed inline in typical 19 mm spacing if they are directly electrically connected to the conductive base plate of the standard's box. Even bulky copper base would have some $100 \mu\Omega$ of resistance, so 10% relative difference between 4T and 4TP measurement as shown in Fig.2 will appear for $1 \text{ m}\Omega$ nominal resistance!

Practical example of the ground impedance effect is shown in Fig. 4. The DC resistance (black cross) was measured in 4T definition (ignoring the shield impedance \hat{Z}_{G}). The measured shield impedance of the standard was $\hat{Z}_{\text{G}} \approx 230 \mu\Omega$. The red trace shows 4TP reference measurement of series resistance R_{S} performed by digital sampling bridge that has fully balanced currents in all its coaxial ports, i.e. it measured according to 4TP definition in formula 6. As expected, the R_{S} exhibits fixed offset of roughly $+230 \mu\Omega$ above the DC value, as the \hat{Z}_{G} became part of the measured impedance. However, when the same standard was measured by common RLC bridge Keysight E4980A (blue trace), the results showed offset compared to the reference 4TP measurement (red trace) despite E4980A errors were corrected by another $100 \text{ m}\Omega$ standard. This effect is caused by the poor balance of the current in the potential coaxial ports of the bridge H_{POT} and L_{POT} , i.e. the bridge “ignored” the voltage drop in the shield of the standard. Although the bridge ports contain small coaxial chokes that should improve current balance in the ports, they became effective only at higher frequencies. At low frequencies, the bridge basically measured in 4T definition, resp. 5T definition shown in Fig. 2 on the left and only at higher frequencies the difference between 4TP and 5T definition started to disappear. This effect can be suppressed by insertion of external coaxial chokes to the E4980A ports (green trace). In this case the E4980A bridge matches reference digital 4TP bridge much better. However, long cables wound on the chokes introduce other errors, so the size of chokes is limited. The other RLC bridge models acts similarly. This effect

Figure 4: Example of impedance measurement errors caused by shield impedance ($Z_{\text{G}} \approx 230 \mu\Omega$) of poorly designed standard when measured by bridge with and without balanced currents in its coaxial ports.

may not be apparent for a first look, but it is known to cause a lot of confusion when such standards are being used by different labs on different bridges. E.g. the calibration lab performs calibration in true 4TP definition and user will try to use them for ordinary RLC bridges which inevitably results into large offsets of real component of impedance. Therefore, low impedance standards of construction shown in Fig. 3 are rarely used below some 10Ω . It is generally not recommended even with true 4TP bridge setups, because the internal impedance \hat{Z} may be very stable in order of ppm/K, but the voltage drop between the ports may not due to unstable shield and/or contact resistances. Therefore, the effect is often suppressed by modified connection of the standard's grounds as shown in Fig. 5. By splitting the ground circuit for the current ports H_{CUR} and L_{CUR} and potential ports H_{POT} and L_{POT} , the current path return current \hat{I}_{CH} no longer flows via the shield impedance \hat{Z}_{G} and thus there is minimized voltage drop \hat{U}_{G} . It will never be zero, because there are mutual couplings inside the standard, but it will be greatly reduced. In some cases the grounds are connected in the middle as shown in Fig. 5, but in some cases the grounds are totally split. In conclusion, when measuring low impedances, the only reasonable advice is to always check the method of connection of grounds of 4TP standards before they are used and preferably avoid low impedance types when all four BNCs are simply mounted on common metal plate.

Figure 5: 4TP standard with suppressed shield impedance.

1.1 Adapters

Unavoidable part of any impedance measurement is proper interconnection between the bridge and calibrated device (UUT). Whereas RLC bridges often use four BNCs for 4TP measurements, the actual components to be measured are typically two terminal (2T) devices such as resistor, capacitor or battery as in case of EIS measurements. Obviously, an adapter must be used to traverse between the two types of physical connections. Some of the examples were shown in [14]. The main problem for the higher impedances and frequencies below say 100 kHz lies in avoiding capacitive leakage between High and Low terminals. That is relatively easy to solve by insertion of metallic shields connected to the measurement ground of RLC meter (guarding). However, for low impedance measurements, the situation is more complex. It is necessary to take into account not only series impedances of the interconnection joints, but also mentioned ground impedance problems and mutual couplings between cables and leads. There are several techniques how to minimize these effects.

1.1.1 4TP to 2/4-wire interfacing

Most common situation is connection of 4TP bridge equipped by four coaxial ports to two terminal (2T) or four terminal (4T) UUT. Practical example is shown in Fig. 6. UUT is impedance simulator box in

Figure 6: Example of adapter between two terminal standard and 4TP bridge. a) Photo, b) front view, c) side view.

a shape of larger lithium cell with two screw terminals. Practical inner solution of the standard is not relevant, however the important aspect are its terminals. Each of the terminals was split into two separate coaxial terminals. The inner one is used for potential measurement whereas the outer one is used for supplying measurement current. In order to connect such standard to a 4TP bridge, the H_{CUR} and L_{CUR}

coaxial cables are connected to the current terminals and their coaxial shields are interconnected to ensure proper return path for the measurement current. Important rule is to keep the non-coaxial parts of the connection as short as possible as well as the ground joint between the two cables. The non-coaxial part of the connection should be rigid, so it cannot change geometry easily. The potential cables H_{POT} and L_{POT} are connected in the same manner, i.e. as short as possible non-coaxial path to the terminals and their coaxial grounds connected together. Both ground joints between the H_{CUR} - L_{CUR} and H_{POT} - L_{POT} should be connected together by another ground lug taped roughly in the middle. The four coaxial grounds should never be connected to a star configuration nor mounted on common conductive place as it would introduce the mentioned problem of current return path impedances. The mutual coupling between the potential wires and current wires can be further reduced by bending one of those pairs into 90 degrees angle. This is especially helpful for the non-coaxial parts of the adapter, but it will help even for the coaxial ones since the currents in the cables are never fully balanced and thus still sensitive to mutual couplings.

Figure 7: Example of connection of potential and current test leads to screw terminals.

This example showed connection of standard with specially designed standard with split potential and current terminals. However, it is possible to make similar connection even with actual cell with screw terminals using cleverly made isolating washers as is shown in Fig. 7. Even if the central screw is connected to the base plate of terminal, the isolating washer shortens the common path of current and potential sensing, so the reference plane of measurement shifts closer to the actual cell.

1.1.2 4-wire interfacing

When the standard shown in Fig. 6 is connected to EIS meter equipped by only four non-coaxial leads, the connection may be made according to Fig. 8. In this case the magnetic interference between the current leads and potential leads can be minimized by tightly twisting the current leads and splitting them just before connection to the UUT. The potential lugs can be twisted as well, however the terminals are quite far apart in this case, so there will be still quite long non-twisted portion of the connection. In this particular case it is not even possible to bend the plane of potential wires by 90 degrees as it comes out of the same cable as the current leads. So here it is possible to use principle of symmetry. If the wiring is made symmetrical as in the Fig. 8, the mutual couplings to both potential leads should be roughly equal and thus subtract. The UUT shown in the example in Fig. 6 contains switch for several ranges including internal SHORT correction. The SHORT correction enables subtraction of residual mutual inductances of the adapter, however if it should work properly, the geometry of the adapter wiring must not change when switching the particular ranges of the UUT.

1.1.3 4-wire to 4TP interfacing

Whereas interfacing 4TP to 4-wire seems to be straightforward, the opposite direction is usually not possible without limitations. Connection of 4TP standard (UUT) to 4T bridge equipped by plain current and potential leads may be needed when the UUT is calibration standard to be used to correct RLC bridge's errors (LOAD correction). It is theoretically possible under several conditions. First, UUT grounds must be connected according to Fig. 5, so there should be minimized difference between 4T and 4TP connections. Second, if UUT was calibrated in 4TP defining conditions, it is at least necessary to ensure current return path via the shield of UUT via the H_{CUR} and L_{CUR} ports as was shown in Fig. 9. Lack of this current return path would significantly change reactance of the UUT. However, whenever it is possible, the UUT should be calibrated in the same connection instead of relying on small difference between 4TP connection and Fig. 9.

Figure 8: Example of adapter between two terminal standard and 4T/5T bridge.

Figure 9: Possible connection of 4TP standard to 4T bridge using plain potential and current leads.

1.2 Concept of SHORT correction

In impedance metrology there are usually two ways of expressing impedance: (i) absolute and (ii) relative. First, most common in primary labs and/or for use with true 4TP bridges, is “absolute” impedance according to 4TP defining conditions. The impedance is given exactly as measured at the reference plane of standard’s ports under three conditions: Zero current from H_{POT} port, zero voltage at L_{POT} port and fully balanced currents in all ports. However, the 4TP connection is rarely used for practical measurements of impedance. Some kind of adapter is used to traverse from bridge connectors to UUT as described earlier. Such adapter always introduces some parasitic components as shown in model in Fig. 10. The parasitics comprise from series impedance R_S and L_S of non-four wire section of the adapter and combined mutual couplings M_{EF} in the wiring of the adapter. Both form effective residual series impedance \hat{Z}_S which adds up to the measured impedance \hat{Z}_X of the UUT. Therefore, for practical measurements, the RLC bridge/EIS meter always implements some kind of zeroing of effective series impedance of terminals (SHORT correction) and effective parallel shunting admittance between terminals (OPEN correction). The OPEN correction is mainly relevant only for high impedances, whereas SHORT correction for low impedances. The SHORT correction itself is straightforward:

$$\hat{Z}_X = \hat{Z}_{EF} - \hat{Z}_S, \quad (7)$$

where \hat{Z}_{EF} is total measured impedance, \hat{Z}_S is interface effective series impedance and \hat{Z}_X is “true” impedance of the UUT. The OPEN and SHORT corrections allow, up to some level, to eliminate unwanted parasitic impedances in the adapter between the bridge and UUT. Practical problem is of course realization of SHORT. It is relatively straightforward to make “ideal” SHORT module in 4TP connection in Fig. 11. However, in other configurations, such as two-terminal with terminals far apart it

is impossible, because shorting bar will have residual impedance by itself and also mutual coupling in the wiring of interface which will result into some effective combined impedance. It is also not possible to e.g. screw two wires together, because change in geometry of the adapter wiring would again lead to change of its effective mutual couplings. Therefore, for practical reasons, it is common to express impedance of UUT as relative to residual impedance of some well defined SHORTing module, which will then be used by user of the UUT standard itself. Every calibration certificate of an impedance standard should clearly mention if the expressed impedance is related to particular SHORT or absolute one. If not mentioned and procedure mentions no SHORT standard in the list of equipment, it is almost always the absolute mode. However, for low impedance measurements it should be clarified with certificate issuing institution.

Figure 10: Parasitic components of adapter (left) and equivalent SHORT correction model (right).

The SHORTing standard is internally constructed in such a way it should exhibit minimal effective impedance. If made properly in 4TP connection, the residual impedance can be even below $1 \mu\Omega$ at low frequencies. It is often considered as “ideal” zero despite its residual impedance grows with frequency. Therefore, as mentioned above, it is good practice to always calibrate especially low impedance standards relative to particular SHORTing standard and express the values in calibration certificate relative to residual impedance of SHORTing standard. This ensures compatible measurement conditions in calibration lab and user of the standard. Another type of zeroing standard is so called 0Ω standard. The difference

Figure 11: 4TP coaxial cable connection of SHORT correction (left) and practical example of SHORT module from Hewlett Packard 16074A set.

between SHORT and 0Ω standards is the 0Ω standard is not trying to reach zero impedance. Instead, it is internally designed with some kind of shorting bar/joint in identical geometry as the other standards of the set under assumption the residual resistance and especially reactance will be identical. Therefore, the relative impedance will have orders of magnitude lower series inductance component. The bridge needs not to make any other step to use 0Ω standard. The zeroing (SHORT correction) is simply performed with the 0Ω standard connected instead of SHORT.

Example of 4TP SHORT correction cables connection is shown in Fig. 11. Note the coaxial connectors are mounted via isolation washers, so the return current flows via the cables inside the box instead

of metal case. Otherwise there would be significant mutual coupling between the parallel sections of the cables and thus certain effective inductance. Practical example of old Hewlett Packard HP16074A standard is shown in Fig. 11 on the right. It is also common to connect the same SHORT topology externally using BNC cables and T-adapters. Modern solution to SHORT (and the standards in general) is use of strip lines on printed circuit boards as shown in Fig. 12. Use of PCB is practical due to much better geometrical repeatability and also price.

Figure 12: SHORT module made using strip lines on four layer PCB.

Visually interesting example of impedance standards set built with zero $0\ \Omega$ correction is Hewlett Packard 16074A. Detailed picture of internal structure is shown in Fig. 13. Geometry of $0\ \Omega$ and $100\ \text{m}\Omega$ stayed the same, except the thin ridge in the middle which makes the resistive element. All four BNCs are mounted directly to metal plate, so there is ground impedance, but it should be roughly the same for all standard in the set, so the effect will be eliminated by the bridge SHORT correction. However, if the bridge would be zeroed by SHORT correction from the set (Fig. 11), the resulting relative impedance would be hardly usable.

Figure 13: Inside of Hewlett Packard 16074A impedance standards set. Top: $0\ \Omega$ standard with solid metal shunting plate. Bottom: $100\ \text{m}\Omega$ standard.

1.2.1 4-wire short

Whereas short arrangement in 4TP connection is quite straight forward, it is not so simple and effective in 4-wire connection. 4-wire short must be connected in such a way the mutual coupling between potential and current leads is minimized and current flowing via the current leads joint does not produce voltage drop on the potential terminals joint. At the same time, low test leads should be connected together,

because impedance bridge may not be able to handle totally floating potential leads. Example of simple connection with banana terminals is shown in Fig. 14 on the left. Important is to keep the order so current is not flowing via the potential bananas. Alternatively, it is possible to make a shoring adapter with banana sockets as shown in Fig. 14 on the right. In both cases twisting of the test leads reduces their mutual coupling, so parasitic reactance X_S is minimized.

Twisting the leads is critical in order to achieve low reactance errors. Fig. 15 shows example with typical values of mutual coupling to be expected. The twisted part exhibits almost no mutual coupling even when the twisted bundles lies on each other. Worst case estimate is $M_{EF} \approx \pm 5 \text{ nH}$ per 10 cm of leads, which is roughly $X_{EF} \approx \pm 150 \mu\Omega$. That is in fact pessimistic estimate. Real coupling when the bundles are at least centimeter apart will be lower than 2 nH. However, when the twisting ends near the short adapter (or UUT), even small loop shown in example in Fig. 15 will have parasitic inductance of $M_{EF} \approx \pm 50 \text{ nH}$, i.e. $X_{EF} \approx \pm 1.5 \text{ m}\Omega$. That may be already significant offset when large cell impedances are measured. Fortunately, the mutual coupling drops fast, when the potential and current leads are kept at least few centimeters apart.

Figure 14: Simple 4-wire short connection with banana test leads: simple banana connection (left), connection via adapter with sockets (right)

Figure 15: Example of parasitic mutual coupling between 4-wire leads.

2 Reference impedance bridge

Project LiBforSecUse [9] calls for design of reference impedance bridge for purposes of calibration of reference impedance standards which are then used for calibration of commercially available RLC/EIS meters. Therefore, the design is not directly dedicated for measurement of batteries, however it may be eventually used in that manner as well. According to the requirements of the LiBforSecUse project, the bridge must be capable of following:

1. Frequency range 0.01 Hz to 5 kHz.
2. Impedance range at least $1\ \Omega$ down to $1\ \text{m}\Omega$.
3. Measurement in full complex plane.
4. Measurement in presence of DC bias voltage at least 0 to 5 V.
5. AC measurement current up to 2 A, eventually DC bias current up to 2 A.
6. Measurement in 4TP and 4T (5T) definitions.
7. Preferably use of commonly available HW components.
8. Target expanded uncertainty below 1% at $1\ \text{m}\Omega$ impedance.

Possibly the simplest method of measurement of low impedance is use of digital sampling technique, so it was chosen for the design. This also allowed use of already existing digital sampling and processing tool TWM [7], so only additional algorithm for processing the digitized voltage waveforms from the digitizers to the measured impedance was needed. The TWM tool already solved all problems related to corrections of the digitizers' errors. Initial choice of the digitizers was to use common sampling multimeters Keysight 3458A [3], however it turned out it may be more practical to use low cost cDAQ digitizers such as NI 9238/9239 from National Instrument [11]. Nevertheless, TWM tool is flexible enough so it can operate both digitizer types (and several others) without any changes in designed topology. So, following text will always show HP 3458A digitizers in the diagrams, however it is replaceable by any other supported digitizer in the TWM tool.

2.1 Selection of measurement topology

Following section will discuss possible connections of the digital sampling bridge for low impedances. Relatively high target calibration uncertainty of 1% at $1\ \text{m}\Omega$ impedances gives a variety of options. Several possible connections will be discussed with their specific problems and benefits. Basic sampling bridge topology is shown in Fig. 16. The selected source of measurement harmonic signal is any low noise synthesizer (in this case NI 9260 [12]). It is beneficial to choose such synthesizer, which can be synchronized with the digitizers in order to achieve coherent sampling for simplest possible data processing of the digitized waveforms using Fourier transform (see section 2.3). The power amplifier used to generate main measurement current via the impedances may be even some ordinary laboratory voltage amplifier capable to operate into low impedance loads. However, for low impedances it is always safer to use transconductance amplifier (TA), whose feedback will keep the set current level automatically. For measurements without presence of high DC bias voltage, any TA will work. Very pleasant experience was achieved with old Datron 4600 amplifier, which provides floating output and the desired currents without significant harmonic distortion or noise. However, for measurement in presence of DC bias offset, the Datron 4600 has insufficient allowed appliance voltage (up to some 3 V only). Therefore, Fluke 52120A was considered for the higher DC bias voltages as it can operate up to 7 V. At this point it is important to note when TA is used for supplying capacitance, it may result in gradual buildup of DC bias voltage depending on initial phase of the synthesizer, because capacitor will act as integrator of measurement current. This undesirable effect can be suppressed by connecting a discharging resistor in parallel to the output of the TA.

One of the basic challenges of the bridge design is achieving balanced current at least in the current coaxial cable. At higher frequencies it can be enforced by placement of a coaxial choke, however it has no effect at frequencies below few hertz. Therefore, the current output of the TA was connected as shown

Figure 16: Basic connection of 4T/5T digital sampling bridge.

in Fig. 16, i.e. the current flows via the UUT impedance Z_2 to the reference impedance Z_1 and then returns back via the coaxial shield of the cable. This simple solution ensures almost perfect balance of current is the main current cable with exception of leakages from the potential ports H_{POT} and L_{POT} of Z_2 . This was achieved for a cost of violating one of 4TP defining conditions - zero potential at L_{POT} port of Z_2 . This cannot be achieved without some form of balancing circuit which would complicate the bridge design. Fortunately, it is not critical for low impedances at low frequencies.

The reference impedance Z_1 should be preferably a coaxial current shunt which can be manufactured in range down to few milliohms and easily calibrated in terms of phase error, ac-dc transfer and DC resistance to order of less than microradian per kilohertz and 10^{-6} for ac-dc transfer and DC resistance. Furthermore, coaxial shunt design greatly reduces effects of mutual couplings between its input and output ports. The voltage drop at the shunt is digitized by digitizer DMM 1. Choice of reference impedance Z_1 nominal value is compromise between two contradicting requirements: (i) The highest possible amplitude of signal at DMM 1 for good SNR, (ii) The lowest possible common mode voltage at DMM 2 to limit common mode rejection errors. Roughly $200\text{ m}\Omega$ impedance seems to be acceptable compromise for the desired currents up to 2 A and 1 V range of digitizer for most of the measured impedances. Exception may be measurement of microohm impedances, where choice of lower reference impedance may be beneficial.

The voltage drop on the UUT impedance Z_2 is digitized by digitizer DMM 2. For simplicity, the shield voltages of the Z_2 are ignored and only live terminals difference is measured in this case so it is 4T measurement of 4TP standard. The problem arising from this topology is non-zero common mode voltage at L_{POT} port of Z_2 . This means there will be capacitive current leaking from the L_{POT} terminal via the Guard of DMM 2 and its capacitance C_{GE} to ground. This capacitance exceeds nanofarad, so Spice simulation of this topology showed errors up to order 0.1 % can be expected at 5 kHz.

Therefore, another variation of the topology was considered. The connection is shown in Fig. 17. In this case, the polarity of the input terminals of DMM 2 was inverted and the guard of the DMM 2 is supplied from H_{CUR} port. This way, the ground current via the capacitance C_{GE} was diverted from the potential ports of the Z_2 , so the leakage should cause errors only in order of 0.01 %. However, effectiveness of this trivial solution depends on potential drop between the H_{POT} terminal and the joint, where the guard voltage is extracted. It will depend on internal impedances of the standard Z_2 which cannot be affected, so it is not always the best solution.

Far better solution of the capacitive leakage currents is shown in Fig. 18. In this case, the ground capacitance C_{GE} is supplied from a guard buffer placed at the input of the multimeter. This guard buffer can easily have ground shunting capacitance below 10 pF, so the capacitive leakage is reduced about 100 times for the HP 3458A. Furthermore, the guarding voltage can be used to actively shield the input cable by using triaxial cable as shown in Fig. 18. This solution enables measurement of impedances even above $1\ \Omega$ with errors below some 0.007 % at 5 kHz (according the Spice simulation). However, it is still just a 4T measurement and it is also not capable to effectively deal with DC bias voltage.

Figure 17: Modified connection of 4T digital sampling bridge: reduction of ground leakage by using guard of the digitizer.

Figure 18: Modified connection of 4T digital sampling bridge: reduction of ground leakage by using guarding buffer.

If there is a DC bias present at the standard Z_2 , the DMM2 will have to operate with relatively high DC voltage of approximately 4 V (lithium cell) and comparatively small AC voltage drop proportional to the measured impedance (millivolts). It is not possible to simply use AC coupling mode of the digitizer, when measuring frequencies such as 0.1 Hz, because AC-mode bandwidth of the digitizers starts at few hertz. So there are two options: (i) DC and AC must be digitized together at higher voltage range (10 V for HP 3458A) which means poor amplitude resolution, (ii) The DC must be eliminated externally. Measurements showed the performance of the HP 3458A at shorter aperture times (for frequencies above few hundred hertz) would be adequate for measurements with uncertainties only in order of 0.1 % for 1 m Ω impedance. The NI 9239 performs a bit better with errors in order of 0.01 % for the same impedance for any frequency up to 5 kHz. If better uncertainty is needed, the DC bias must be removed externally, so lower voltage range of DMM2 can be used.

Possible extension of the bridge design for 4TP measurements with optional suppression of the DC bias is shown in Fig. 19. The reference DMM1 stayed connected as it was before except its guard is supplied from input of the reference shunt. This causes minor improvement of uncertainty if the current cable has higher voltage drop on its shield. The potential of the Z_2 is measured using two sampling multimeters DMM2 and DMM3, each of them measuring voltage on one potential port of Z_2 . The

Figure 19: Connection of 4TP digital sampling bridge for low impedances with DC bias subtractors.

impedance is then calculated from their difference:

$$\hat{Z}_X = \frac{\hat{U}_3 - \hat{U}_2}{\hat{U}_1}, \quad (8)$$

where \hat{U}_1 , \hat{U}_2 and \hat{U}_3 are complex voltages measured by the three digitizers. If the input differential impedance \hat{Z}_{IN2} of the DMM2 is known, it can be used to calculate value of Z_2 impedance with correction to the shunting effect:

$$\hat{Z}_2 = \frac{(\hat{U}_3 - \hat{U}_2)\hat{Z}_1\hat{Z}_{IN2}}{\hat{U}_1\hat{Z}_{IN2} + \hat{U}_2\hat{Z}_1}. \quad (9)$$

This improves measurement accuracy mainly above 1Ω at higher frequencies, as the digitizers and their input cables may have capacitance in order of hundreds of picofarads.

The circuit also shows possible method of elimination of the DC biases coming from the UUT Z_2 . Two floating controlled DC sources were placed in series with the inputs of the DMM2 and DMM3. These can be iteratively set, so the DC components at the digitizer inputs disappear, so the lower voltage ranges can be selected. In the simplest case it can be even a battery with a potentiometer connected in series with High inputs. However, for practical reasons the guard buffers in the prototype were accompanied by 18bit DACs, so the voltage subtractors may be programmed digitally with resolution around $50\mu\text{V}$. The critical feature of such circuit is ensuring guarding of the buffer and DC subtractor itself from the ground to prevent leakages via the unit itself. Practical realisation will be shown later.

The one remaining problems of the topology is however a presence of common mode voltage at L_{POT} port of Z_2 . Typical situation is shown in Fig. 20. When reference impedance $Z_1 = 200\text{m}\Omega$, current $I = 1\text{A}$ and UUT is $Z_2 = 10\text{m}\Omega$, there will be large common mode voltage $U_{CM} \approx 200\text{mV}$ at both digitizers DMM2 and DMM3 and comparatively small difference of $U_{Z2} = 10\text{mV}$ between them. Therefore, any difference of gain, phase and amplitude transfer (linearity) between the DMM2 and DMM3 will cause large errors on the measured difference voltage U_{Z2} . The situation will become even worse for lower impedances. Situation can be improved by choice of lower nominal value of the reference impedance Z_1 , but it will be for a cost of worse SNR or DMM1 signal and also the digitized voltage will fall in the lower portion of the DMM1 range, which is usually strongly nonlinear.

Therefore, one last modification of the topology is possible in order to suppress the common mode problems. The diagram is shown in Fig. 21. In this case, an adapter is connected between the DMM2 and DMM3 inputs and potential ports of Z_2 . This adapter ensures DMM3 is measuring ordinary 4T

Figure 20: Connection of 4TP digital sampling bridge for low impedances: problem of common mode voltage.

Figure 21: Connection of 4TP digital sampling bridge for low impedances in 2x4T measurement mode.

definition impedance (voltage drop between the live terminals of potential ports). The other digitizer DMM2 is measuring potential drop between shields of the potential ports of Z_2 , which is essentially another 4T measurement, hence this method will be called 2x4T in following text. By combining the two 4T measurements it is possible to obtain equivalent 4TP impedance:

$$\hat{Z}_2 = \frac{\hat{U}_2 + \hat{U}_3}{\hat{U}_2}. \quad (10)$$

The diagram also shows final selected solution of the guarding buffers which were extended for use of shielded twinaxial cables. In this connection, both High and Low input conductors are guarded, so they

exhibit no differential capacitance. The Low guard also supplies eventual guard of the digitizer, so there it also no ground leakage. Therefore, correction for capacitive leakages can be ignored for impedances Z_2 below some $10\ \Omega$. Only correction that should be taken into account is shunting of the Z_2 by input impedance of the DMM3, which is some $270\ \text{pF}$ for HP 3458A multimeter, however even for $5\ \text{kHz}$ and $10\ \Omega$ capacitive reactance, the effect would be below $0.01\ \%$, which would be likely masked by other sources of uncertainty, such as linearity of DMM3. Note the circuit also contains $10\ \text{mH}$ coaxial choke placed at the current cable and reference ground was moved to the Z_1 standard, which ensured zero ground potential at least at one of the impedances. The choke will have effect only at frequencies above few hundred hertz. At lower frequencies the circuit relies on floating output of the amplifier.

2.1.1 Guarding buffer and DC bias eliminator

Some of the topologies shown above uses guarding buffers with optional DC bias subtractor. Example of a prototype of such buffers will be described in following paragraphs. The prototype contains two

Figure 22: Dual guarding unit with floating DC source for subtraction of DC bias voltage.

identical channels required e.g. for DMM2 and DMM3. The principle of operation of one channel of the designed unit is shown in Fig. 22. The floating module connects 18bit floating D/A converter AD5781 with output buffer in series with the live signal conductor. Output of the buffer is decoupled by large capacitance as its only purpose is to amplify D/A output. Therefore, the buffer transfer has no effect to the passing AC signal and does not change the overall linearity of the digitizer. Voltage resolution in the prototype is roughly $40\ \mu\text{V}$ with adjustment range of $\pm 5\ \text{V}$ which is sufficient for single lithium cell DC bias compensation. The key aspect of the module design is minimizing the capacitive leakage from High and Low coaxial conductors to ground. Thus the whole module was carefully guarded. As the DC/DC converters used for supplying the floating D/A and buffer have large coupling capacitance, there are two converters connected in series and the joint between them is connected to the guard driver. This way the coupling capacitance from grounded supply to the guarded area is broken. Only remaining capacitances are the guard driver input capacitance and PCB design imperfections, which are below $10\ \text{pF}$ in total. Both channels (modules) were built and connected to a single controller which allows to set the DC levels manually or via remote interface for automated operation. Picture of the unit is shown in Fig. 23. The two floating units were completely encased into guard-driven metal boxes and placed into another grounded box to prevent capacitive coupling to outside environment.

Note the shielded twinaxial cables used for the inputs of the buffer were not commercially available, so a Tasker C121 twinax cable was used. The cable was then placed into a metal braided sleeve and isolated to flexible heat shrinking tube. A pair of BNC was used for each cable at the buffer side instead of expensive triaxial connectors. The shields of BNCs were connected to the guard drivers and the cable braid was connected via banana plug to ground. Therefore no part of the signal path is unguarded, so

Figure 23: Prototype of dual guarding unit with floating DC source for subtraction of DC bias voltage.

the shunting capacitances were minimized. Stray capacitances of the unshielded BNCs are irrelevant at such low frequencies. The two twinaxial cores of the cable were connected to a single BNC at the measurement side, which adds about 5 pF of shunting capacitance, which is still acceptable. Diagram of cable connection is shown in Fig. 24.

Figure 24: Input/output twinaxial cable connection to the guarding buffer and associated stray capacitances.

2.2 Selection of digitizer

Chapters above discussed design of the measurement topology for general digitizers and inherent errors of the setups due to various parasitic effects in the measurement network itself. However, the uncertainty of the whole setup is also given by the digitizer and its linearity. Following chapters will discuss benefits and disadvantages of particular digitizers.

2.2.1 Keysight 3458A

The designs above assumed use of popular HP 3458A digitizers as the most suitable type as it is abundant even in many private laboratories. Big advantage of HP 3458A is its stability and also its auto-calibration function that is capable to achieve repeatable gain and linearity in order of 10^{-6} . These instruments incorporate internal guard of the whole floating measurement circuitry, so when external guard buffer is used, there is almost non-existent problem of common mode rejection (CMRR) at least for low frequencies. They also, due to complete separation, cannot exhibit crosstalk between several units other than via external cables. On the other hand, these digitizers offer good linearity only from some 10% of full scale

input voltage above. Their linearity starts to exhibit very random shapes below this threshold as it is shown in examples in Fig.25 or Fig. 26. The shape is still measurable for longer aperture times, however when shorter aperture times than $100\ \mu\text{s}$ are used, the linearity shape starts to get much worse and this is the limitation of possible measurements at higher frequencies than few hundred hertz.

Figure 25: Example of amplitude linearity errors of HP 3458A for a frequency of 27 Hz and aperture time of $900\ \mu\text{s}$.

Figure 26: Relative error of HP 3458A and NI9238 AC voltage measurement as function of applied AC amplitude. HP 3458A was configured to range 1 V, sampling rate 5 kSa/s, aperture of $120\ \mu\text{s}$. NI 9238 was configured to 50 kSa/s. Frequency of test signal was 60 Hz.

The situation with 3458A multimeters starts to get even more complicated in presence of DC bias voltage, if it is not eliminated by some of the above mentioned topologies. Analysis of the AC errors of various digitizers was performed in scope of [6]. Example of results of absolute AC errors due to the DC bias presence at voltage range 10 V is shown in Fig. 27. The errors for long aperture times are below $\pm 100\ \text{nV}$, so for $1\ \text{m}\Omega$ impedance and 1 A of measurement current, it will result in some 0.01% errors of measurement independent of DC bias. However, for shorter aperture times needed for higher measurement frequencies, very random errors dependent on the applied DC bias appears, which limits the achievable uncertainty to above 0.2% for the same conditions. The errors are inversely proportional to measured impedance, so for higher impedances it may be sufficient for the target uncertainty of measurement. Note the observed absolute errors were almost independent of test AC voltage.

Although HP 3458A multimeter provides single channel sampling, it is fortunately possible to synchronize multiple units. The problem was described to details e.g. in TWM tool manual [1] or in [4]. There numerous possibilities, however there is in principle only one common technique of synchronization without modifying HW of 3458A. It is shown in Fig. 28. This method is called Master-Slave, because all Slave multimeters are synchronized to Master's sample clock pulses outputted from its EXT OUT output. The Master multimeter can be (i) Free running using its internal TIMER to produce the sample clock, (ii) Synchronized to external sample clock source, (iii) Synchronized to external clock divided by appropriate clock divider. Free running method (i) is simplest, but it would result in asynchronous operation with the DDS synthesizer. See chapter 2.3 for more details on DDS to ADC synchronization modes. In any

Figure 27: Absolute error of 3458A AC voltage measurement as function of DC voltage for various apertures T_A . Range: ± 10 V, sampling mode: “DCV”, applied rms AC voltage: $100 \mu\text{V}$ and 16 Hz. Expanded uncertainty was approx. $0.06 \mu\text{V}$ for all spots.

case the Master-Slave synchronization always results into pseudorandom jitter ± 100 ps given by their internal timing resolution. The effect of the jitter is however suppressible by longer integration times, so it is irrelevant in this application.

Figure 28: Synchronization of multiple 3458A multimeters to external clock source using Master-Slave mode.

2.2.2 National Instruments NI 9238 or NI 9239

Due to the limitations of HP 3458A digitizers another possible candidates were analyzed in scope of [6]. First, the ± 10 V, four channel cDAQ module NI 9239 was tested. It is a 24bit digitizer with fully floating inputs. It has no guarding, so there is possibility of interchannel crosstalk and also limited CMRR, however it still seemed usable at least for the low frequencies. The test to the AC error dependence on the DC bias was performed same as for the HP 3458A. The result is shown in Fig. 29. The AC errors seems to lie mostly under ± 100 nV, so this digitizer seems to be able to reach errors around 0.01% for $1 \text{ m}\Omega$ impedance. Disadvantage of the digitizers is however its limited interchannel gain and phase stability. It can be corrected, however it will typically not stay below some 0.002% for longer than few days, so for highest accuracy, the channels must be often recalibrated.

Another test of AC linearity without presence of DC bias was performed with NI 9238 which is ± 500 mV version of NI 9239. Its lower voltage range is sufficient for the expected bridge operating range and provides better resolution. The AC deviation are shown in Fig. 26. The shape seems to be more

Figure 29: Absolute error of NI9239 AC voltage measurement as function of DC voltage for various applied rms voltages. Expanded uncertainties for particular AC levels were $\{0.06; 0.06 \text{ and } 0.2\} \mu\text{V}$.

monotonic compared to HP 3458A so less density of voltage steps was needed to obtain usable linearity correction. Additionally, the errors with ultra low voltages were measured and shown in Fig. 30.

Figure 30: Absolute AC voltage error of NI9238 for ultra low voltages, configured to sampling rate 50 kSa/s, test frequency 60 Hz.

Crosstalk with low driving impedance is below some 120 dB up to at least 5 kHz. This seems acceptable, however when having the reference impedance of 200 m Ω , the crosstalk will result in $\pm 0.2 \mu\Omega$ uncertainty of the measured impedance due to coupling from DMM 1 and DMM 3 and another $\pm 0.2 \mu\Omega$ uncertainty due to coupling from DMM 3 to DMM 2 (2x4T bridge connection). This is necessary to take into account for very low impedance measurements.

The problem with crosstalk is caused by lack of internal shield between the floating input circuits of particular inputs of the 9238/9239. PCB of the NI9238 is shown in Fig. 31. Bottom side of the PCB is approx 3 mm from grounded metal shield of the unit, so capacitive coupling of the neighboring channels is minimal. However, the top side has a distance of some 10 mm to the shield, so capacitive coupling is possible. Therefore, an experimental modification was made by placing grounded metal plate isolated by PTFE tape on top of the input circuits. Metal ribs were placed between the input connectors and extended outside, so the particular channels are shielded from each other as shown in Fig. 32 on the left. The crosstalk was reduced below -130 dB. The suppression of crosstalk was further improved by grounding the unused channel AI1 as shown in Fig. 32 on the right. Grounding the unused channels of NI9238 for 4T bridge with just two channels is sufficient solution even without the additional metal shielding.

CMRR of the NI9238 is basically given by shunting capacitance of the floating input circuits to ground. This parameter could be theoretically improved by inserting guard metal plates over and under each input channel circuits instead of the ground plate shown in Fig. 32. However such solution was not yet tested and it would be problematic to guard the input connectors.

One more problem related to the NI9238 is its high input capacitance. There is large capacitor placed in parallel to the input possibly to improve ESD protection level and thus total input capacitance is over 600 pF. The capacitor was experimentally removed so the capacitance dropped to approx. 120 pF.

Figure 31: PCB of National Instruments digitizer NI 9238 (bottom on the left, top side on the right).

Figure 32: Left: Modified top side of PCB of National Instruments digitizer NI 9238. Right: connection of the input channels.

2.3 Synchronization of DDS and digitizer

Ensuring synchronization between measurement signal source (DDS) and digitizer(s) is important problem to solve. When DDS operates asynchronously to the digitizer, it is still possible to use FFT based algorithms for complex voltage ratio measurements, but for a cost of additional noise in the measurement and possible problems of aliasing. Described measurement SW supports also fitting based algorithm for data processing, but is still not good option especially when the analyzed signals are close to the noise level. Therefore, it is always best option to synchronise DDS and digitizer sampling rates and set the sampling parameters so the setup operates with coherent sampling. That is digitized waveform window contains always integer number of measurement signal periods. Thus ordinary FFT with rectangular window can be used for complex voltage measurement. To achieve this condition, it is (i) necessary to somehow synchronize (phase lock) sampling rate of digitizer and frequency of DDS generator, (ii) set sampling parameters to achieve coherent sampling. There are numerous ways to achieve these conditions depending on selected HW components. Following chapter will focus on few common situations.

First let's assume sampling with HP 3458A and generation of measurement signal by generic DDS generator or calibrator. The diagram is shown in Fig. 33. The measurement signal is generated by one DDS generator (or calibrator) that is phase locked to local 10 MHz reference. The sampling clock for HP 3458A digitizer is set freely using another DDS synthesizer generating TTL pulses output and it also phase locked to external 10 MHz reference. Alternatively it is possible to use two channel DDS generator for both signals. In this configuration it is possible to achieve almost any ratio of measurement signal frequency and sample clock for HP 3458A limited only by frequency resolution of chosen DDS generators. Thus achieving the coherent sampling condition is trivial.

Figure 33: Synchronization of multiple HP 3458A multimeters and generic DDS signal source to external clock source.

Another situation with HP 3458A digitizers is shown in Fig. 34. Here, the DDS is made of DAC module NI 9260. NI 9260 has internal timebase of 13.1072 MHz, so it is not trivial to phase lock it to local 10 MHz reference. That would require another DDS clock synthesizer inserted between 10 MHz reference and NI 9260. On the other hand it is possible to export sample clock of NI 9260 to PFI0 or PFI1 outputs of cDAQ chassis. This clock is set to maximum rate of the module, i.e. 51.2 kHz in order to achieve reasonable DDS bandwidth. However 51.2 kHz is too much for HP 3458A multimeters as it would require too short aperture times and thus result in high noise and non-linearity. So a variable divider is placed between NI 9260 sample clock source and digitizers to reduce the sampling clock to reasonable rate while still ensuring synchronization. Disadvantage of this method is the actual measurement signal frequency is given by internal timebase of NI 9260 which may deviate up to ± 100 ppm. So when measuring reactance-resistance ratio, it is necessary to consider up to ± 100 ppm deviation in measured value. Note that there is also possibility to import external 10 MHz timebase to NI 9260 exactly as shown in Fig. 33 which would work, but it would result into different sampling rates of NI 9260. It would operate with sampling rate of 39.0625 kHz instead of 51.2 kHz, so the control SW that emulates the DDS function with the DAC must be able to modify its timebase in order to generate actually desired frequencies.

When sampling with NI 9238, there are also several options of synchronization. In the first case shown in Fig. 35 both DDS measurement signal generator and ADC NI 9238 are phase locked to a local 10 MHz reference. NI 9238 ideally operates with 12.8 MHz timebase clock, so there is another DDS pulse generator which converts 10 MHz local reference to required 12.8 MHz TTL clock which is then connected to PFI0 or PFI1 inputs of cDAQ chassis. NI 9238 must be configured to import its timebase clock from one of those inputs. From datasheet it also seems NI 9238 can also operate at much lower timebase frequencies (down to 3.1 MHz), so it should be possible to input 10 MHz timebase directly, but it would lead to change of actual sampling rate same as in case of NI 9260, so the control SW must be able to cope with this. This option was not tested yet.

Another option when sampling with NI 9238 and generating measurement signal with NI 9260 is shown in Fig. 36. In this case the NI 9238 exports its timebase via the cDAQ chassis to NI 9260 DAC DDS synthesizer so no additional HW or external connections are required. However, there are few drawbacks. First, NI 9260 operates with modified timebase rate of 12.8 MHz, so its sampling rate is reduced from

Figure 34: Synchronization of multiple HP 3458A multimeters to DDS DAC synthesizer NI 9260.

Figure 35: Synchronization of NI 9238 and generic DDS to external clock source.

51.2kHz to 50kHz, which must be set in the control SW. Second, NI9238 exports its timebase only when in operation, i.e. when it is digitizing! Therefore the control SW must start digitizing and keep acquisition on background despite the sample data are not needed. The TWM tool (see chapter 2.4) supports this mode of operation. Last problem is the actual measurement frequency is given by internal timebase of ADC NI9238 which may deviate up to ± 100 ppm, so a quadrature measurement (e.g. C-to-R) may deviate up to ± 100 ppm. This must be either corrected or considered as uncertainty source. However actual clock deviations are typically in order of 10^{-6} , so it is not critical.

Figure 36: Synchronization of NI9260 DDS to NI9238 ADC.

2.4 TWM tool as Digital Sampling Bridge

The TWM tool [7] was originally designed for measurement of power and power quality parameters. However, it was from beginning designed as an universal tool for sampling voltage and current waveforms of any number of channels and their processing using Matlab style algorithms. Therefore, it was possible to directly use TWM for digital sampling impedance bridge as it is. Only modification was addition of new instrument drivers (for NI 9238) and one algorithm for calculation of impedance in the configurations shown in previous chapters. This section will describe how to use and setup TWM tool for the impedance measurement in various connections shown above. The section will not show in details general use of the tool and its correction mechanisms as they were already described in the TWM guide [1].

Figure 37: Main panel of TWM tool.

2.4.1 Digitizer setup

First step to configure TWM for low impedance measurement is configuration of digitizers. This guide expects only two main digitizer types (HP 3458A or NI 9238). The configuration menu is invoked by clicking button **Digitizer** in the main TWM window shown in Fig. 37. The panel of digitizer configuration is shown in Fig. 38. In addition to original versions of TWM, one more option was included. TWM tool can now perform time multiplexing. Although it is usable for the bridge operation, it is not described in following text, so make sure the checkbox **Enable multiplexer mode** is disabled. Also it is recommended to use the delayed reset of the digitizers, especially for HP 3458A as it saves the relays. Common rule for all digitizer types in this panel is the particular roles of a digitizer virtual channels is not defined here. This panel only makes a list of virtual channels and maps them to physical instruments and/or their inputs. Roles of the virtual channels are defined later in correction configuration in chapter 2.4.2. Therefore order of the channels is not relevant.

Figure 38: Example of TWM configuration for use of two channel of HP 3458A with sampling clock controlled by AWG Tektronix AFG3101C.

2.4.1.1 HP 3458A

In case of use of HP 3458A, the page **3458A** needs to be selected in the digitizer configuration panel. Example configuration for measurement in 4T definition with two digitizers according the setup shown in Fig. 16 is shown in Fig. 38. The two HP 3458A are synchronized in MASTER-SLAVE mode with AWG Tektronix 3101 used as a sampling clock source for the MASTER unit, so **Synchronization mode** is set to “MASTER-SLAVE, MASTER clocked by AWG”. If the synchronization is made according Fig. 33, the **AWG type** must be set to one of the supported clock generators (Tektronix 3101 in the example). If the synchronization is made according to Fig. 34, the **AWG type** must be set to “dummy”, which means TWM will not try to control the source. Instead, user must ensure correct sampling clock being generated before measurement. The order of HP 3458A in the channels list depends on MASTER-SLAVE(s) units EXT TRIG connections. I.e. MASTER is always first in the list, SLAVE unit(s) are in any order after MASTER.

Input range should be selected accordingly to the expected measured voltage drop and eventually to also cover DC bias voltage. If the reference impedance is e.g 200 mΩ and current up to 1 A, the minimum usable range for reference channel is 1 V as shown in the example. If the UUT impedance will be up to some 500 mΩ, the range of second (UUT) channel has to be also 1 V. However, when UUT value will be only up to say 50 mΩ, the range can be reduced to 100 mV to gain better resolution, linearity and SNR. On the other hand, when the UUT will be measured with DC bias of say 4 V, the range must be set to 10 V to cover full AC+DC voltage. However, keep in mind each range will have different gain-phase errors, so changing ranges will require individual calibrations. Thus it may be more practical to keep fixed, non-optimal range, covering all measured UUT values.

Useful feature of the HP 3458A driver is automatic aperture time selection. User may choose to always enter it manually in the main measurement panel (**Aperture selection mode** to “Manual”), however it may be convenient to make simple rules list as shown in the example and set **Aperture selection mode** to “Table”. TWM will then automatically pick one of the predefined apertures based on the selected sampling rate which makes calibration and use of TWM much easier as the digitizers need not to be calibrated for many different apertures. Validity of the configuration may be tested by pressing **TEST**. Identifiers of all instruments defined by their addresses should appear in the **Identification/status** field.

Note the driver in current version of TWM also theoretically supports new Fluke 8588A. However, there are several versions of FW of this new sampling DMM and even the last one (Version 1.26) seems to not work properly in digitizing mode when data transfer mode is set to integers, so it will most likely not work yet.

Figure 39: Example of configuration of TWM for three channels of NI 9238 digitizer when exporting NI 9238 internal master clock reference.

2.4.1.2 NI 9238

In case of use of NI 9238 the page **cDAQ ADC** is selected as shown in the example in Fig. 39. In the example the single digitizer module NI 9238 was connected to chassis no. 1, slot no. 2, thus the **Device** was set to “cDAQ1Mod2” for all three used virtual channels. Module channels 0, 2 and 3 were used, so the **Channel id** were set accordingly. Note for the simple 4T measurement according Fig. 16 only two digitizer channels would be required.

As mentioned in the section 2.3, the simplest way of using NI 9238 is according to Fig. 36, i.e. to lock DDS synthesizer NI 9260 master clock to NI 9238 internal master clock. To achieve that, the **Digitizer master clock mode** must be set to “Export master clock”. This will export NI 9238 internal master clock to cDAQ chassis so it can be later imported by another device(s). Unfortunately, the NI 9238 does not export clock when not digitizing, so TWM will start digitizing process at background immediately after pressing button **TEST** and it dumps sample data until they are needed. The success will be indicated by the green indicator **Digitizer process is running** and list of detected channels in **Identification/status** field. In some cases when the load of PC is too high, the process may be terminated. That will be indicated by TWM error when measurement is started. Disadvantage of this solution is, the sampling rate must be defined fixed at this point using field **Fixed sampling rate** and cannot be changed during normal operation of TWM. To achieve full bandwidth, the rate should be preferably set to its maximum value of 50 kSa/s as shown in the example. Note the **Selected MasterClock reference name** string is clock source name to be used by the NI 9260 driver when importing Master clock.

Example of alternative setup when importing master clock from external source according Fig. 35 is shown in Fig. 40. However, even in this case the sampling rate is fixed and must be defined here.

Figure 40: Example of configuration of TWM for three channels of NI 9238 digitizer when importing external master clock reference from cDAQ chassis input PFI0.

2.4.2 Corrections setup - mapping of channels to impedance standards

Next step of configuration of TWM for measurement of impedance is setup of the transducers. This is done by pressing button **HW correction** on the main panel. Tab **Transducers** of the corrections panel is used to define roles of particular virtual digitizer channels defined in digitizer setup above. TWM was originally designed for measurement of power and PQ parameters only. Thus it can either measure single input channel parameters, such as THD, Flicker and various harmonic analysis parameters or it can measure two input channel parameters, i.e. power. For impedance measurement the two input channel algorithm is needed, however TWM allows only combination of voltage and current transducer type for this case. So in order to tell the impedance algorithm which of the digitizer virtual channels is connected to reference impedance and UUT impedance, the voltage and current transducer corrections are used.

Example for 4T measurement according to Fig. 16 is shown in Fig. 41. The first transducer is a 200 mΩ current shunt correction mapped to a first virtual channel of digitizer (set by **ADC high**). This is reference impedance of the bridge and the algorithm uses the calibration file of the shunt as a reference impedance. Control **ADC low** is always set to “Not used” for the reference shunt. The second transducer must be of type voltage divider, i.e. voltage channel and it is so called dummy correction having unity transfer (the dummy correction file is attached to every build of TWM). It is mapped to digitizer’s virtual channel no. 2. This is the UUT impedance channel and the **ADC low** is set to “Not used” in this configuration as we measure in 4T definition.

One additional digitizer virtual channel must be mapped in case of 4TP measurement according to Fig. 19 or Fig. 21. This is done by setting **ADC low** of the second, UUT, transducer to the third virtual channel of digitizer as shown in example in Fig. 42.

Digitizer corrections are made in a usual way following TWM user guide [1].

Figure 41: Example of configuration of TWM transducers for 4T measurement of impedance. First transducer is reference impedance, second transducer is UUT impedance.

Figure 42: Example of configuration of TWM transducers for 4TP measurement of impedance. First transducer is reference impedance, second transducer is UUT impedance using two digitizer channels (differential mode).

2.4.3 Measurement setup

Next step is to configure new measurement. The measurement configuration panel shown in Fig. 43 is invoked by pressing **SETUP MEASUREMENT** or **SETUP & START** buttons on the main panel. The NI 9238 was used in the example, so both **Sampling rate** and **Aperture** are disabled. For HP 3458A it would be necessary to set **Sampling rate** and eventually **Aperture** manually. Next parameter to set is **Meas. time** or **Samples count**. Ideally, the drive signal frequency f_0 , sampling rate f_S and samples count N should be set so a coherent sampling is achieved. There are numerous approaches to calculate such combination, however in case of fixed f_S and f_0 generated by DDS synthesizer with fine frequency resolution, the simplest approach is following formula:

$$f'_0 = \text{round} \left(f_0 \cdot \frac{N}{f_S} \right) \cdot \frac{f_S}{N}, \quad (11)$$

where N is desired record length given in samples, f_0 is desired measurement frequency and f'_0 is actual measurement frequency to be used aligned to nearest possible coherent setup. To make it simple, when the $f_S = 50000$ Hz and $N = 50000$ samples (i.e. 1 s record length), any measurement frequency f_0 with step $f_S/N = 1$ Hz will be coherent, so when the ratio f_S/N is chosen wisely, it is not even necessary to calculate anything. Note although the algorithm would work even with non-coherent sampling, it is strongly advised to always use coherent setup.

Next item to set is **Records count**, which is number of repeated measurements to be performed. **Sub-records**

Figure 43: TWM measurement setup for impedance measurement with NI9238 digitizers.

count should be set to 1 by default. It can be set higher than one only for “WFFT” mode in which case the algorithm will average the FFT spectra in complex domain, which results in better suppression of nonharmonic content in the signal. **Trigger mode** should be set to “Immediate” by default as there is usually no need for synchronizing beginning of sampling to any special external event.

Next step before starting the measurement is to configure the algorithm by pressing **PROCESSING SETUP**. In the window shown in Fig. 44 the tab **QWTB** must be selected. Algorithm “TWM-LowZ” must be selected in the **List of algorithms**. Although all parameters are optional, they should be filled in as follows:

- **f.est** is measurement frequency f_0 . Leaving this field empty may result in significant slowdown of WFFT processing mode as it will try to find the frequency using PSFE algorithm.
- **mode** is signal processing mode. Values can be “WFFT” for windowed Fourier transform (default), “PSFE” for Phase Sensitive Frequency Estimator or “FPNLSF” for 4-parameter non-linear sine fitting. Note only “WFFT” mode was properly tested so far.
- **window** is name of window function used for “WFFT” processing. Default is “rect” when left empty. Use “hanning” when non-coherent sampling is used.
- **equ** is equivalent circuit to which the measured complex impedance will be expressed. List of available options: RsXs, GpBp, Zphid, Zphir, Yphid, Yphir, CpD, CpQ, CpRp, CpGp, CsD, CsQ, CsRs, LsRs, LsQ, Rstau.
- **invert** should be set to 1 when one of the impedances has inverted polarity connection to the digitizer as in Fig. 17. Otherwise leave empty.
- **mode.4TP** is selector of connection mode when UUT impedance is measured in 4TP definition. By default, the value is “4TP”, which means standard connection according to Fig. 19. Alternative

mode is “2x4T” for the modified connection according to Fig. 21. This field has no effect for 4T measurements.

Figure 44: Example of configuration of TWM-LowZ algorithm for measurement of low impedance.

The **processing timeout** should be set to at least 30 seconds to prevent timeouts. The algorithm may take longer time for very long records when measuring low frequencies such as 0.01 Hz, so it may be necessary to extend it. **Time-stamp handling** will have no effect here as long as time multiplexed measurement are not used.

2.4.4 Initiating measurement and troubleshooting

The measurement can be started by **OK** in the new measurement panel or **START** from the main panel. Eventual errors should appear in the main panel **error** window. Most typical issue is wrong setup of sampling rates or apertures or synchronization between digitizers. This typically results in errors involving “timeout...” or “trigger too fast...” messages. Another likely source of error may be overload of the digitizer channel which is checked for every measurement. Short glitches in the measured voltages may sometimes appear when settling after source setup was too short or drive levels were too high. The recorded waveforms may be inspected by clicking **VIEW RECORD**. The waves should be more or less clean sine wave with some amount of noise. Spikes or steps in the waveforms usually signalizes wrong connections or overload of digitizers.

When the waveforms seems ok, but another errors are returned, it is usually related to wrong mapping of digitizers to the standard (problem with transducer corrections) or invalid data in some of the loaded correction (transducers or digitizers) or wrong setup of the algorithm. Typical problem is when sampling rate is e.g. 50 kSa/s, but gain/phase correction contain frequency dependent data only up to say 5 kSa/S. The algorithm than may not be able to perform proper correction in whole bandwidth if acquired data. These sources of errors may sometimes be presented in a bit cryptic way or hard failures of the algorithm itself, so it may be necessary to experiment a bit with correction files. Safest way to identify problem with corrections is to clear digitizer correction and if it does not help also to load “dummy” corrections for both transducers and repeating the measurement. If that does not help, the problem is usually setup of the algorithm. Inspecting GNU Octave console window may help to identify cause of the problem.

When the measurement was performed without errors, but the results seems to not match expected values, it may often be interchanged reference and UUT channel in the transducer mapping. Unstable

Figure 45: Example of TWM-LowZ algorithm output spectra for coherent sampling of 60 Hz signal.

results may be caused by wrong synchronization. The correct synchronization and coherent setup may be inspected using spectrum viewer (clicking **VIEW FFT** in the main panel). The panel shown in Fig. 45 will appear. Note the spectra will be visible only for processing mode “WFFT”. Correct setup should contain sharp single DFT bin peak of the fundamental frequency (60 Hz in the example) and its harmonics with gradually decaying amplitudes. The example also shows 50 Hz mains interference, which unlike the fundamental is not coherent, so the side lobes decays gradually instead of sharp peaks. However, when the interference components are order s of magnitude lower compared to the fundamental components, the effect on the standard deviation of the measurement should be minimal. Example of typical non-coherent sampling results is shown in Fig. 46.

Figure 46: Example of TWM-LowZ algorithm output spectra for non-coherent sampling of 60 Hz signal with rectangular window.

2.4.5 Viewing results

When measurement was successfully performed, the processed results should be available to user. Select “Current” in the **Measurement selection** on the main panel of TWM. The available quantities should appear in the **Results** table as in the example in Fig. 47. The algorithm “TWM-LowZ” returns general information, such as frequency, AC and DC levels on the reference and UUT standards and also power dissipation estimate on the UUT standard. Then it always returns complex impedance in polar form “Z_mod”-“Z_phi”. Next it returns impedance expressed in desired equivalent connection “mjr”-“mnr”. When the bridge is connected in the “2x4T” mode, there will another quantities showing impedance of the coaxial shield which may sometimes be useful information when trying to asses necessity of the 4TP measurement. The results may be exported via the menu accessible by right click in the table of results.

The screenshot displays the TWM-LowZ algorithm results interface. At the top, the 'Measurement selection' is set to 'Current', the 'Selected measurement' is 'test_shunt', and the 'Algorithm selection' is 'Current: TWM-LowZ'. Below these are several configuration options: 'Max. shown dimension' (Scalar), 'Result selection' (Current result), 'Uncertainty display' (None), 'Res. order mode' (Group quantities), 'Convert amplitude' (Amplitude), 'Phase mode' ($\pm \pi$ [rad]), 'Max shown array size' (10), and 'Ref. channel' (None). The 'Info' field shows 'Ready' and the 'Note' field shows 'OZM'. The 'Results' table is shown below, with columns for quantity, avg, ua, and #1. The value for Udc[L1] in the #1 column is highlighted with a red box. A 'Select quantities' menu is open on the right side of the table, listing various quantities like Idc, Udc_ref, Udc, f, Iref, Udut, Pdut, Z_mod, Z_phi, mjr, mnr, mjr_name, mnr_name, spec_f, spec_U, and spec_I.

	avg	ua	#1
Idc[L1]	41.018 3u	0.000 000 000 0	41.018 3u
Udc_ref[L1]	0.000 041 018 3	0.000 000 000 0	0.000 041 018 3
Udc[L1]	38.993 2u	0.000 000 000 0	38.993 2u
f[L1]	60.000 000 00	0.000 000 000 0	60.000 000 00
Iref[L1]	28.928 195 6m	0.000 000 000 0	28.928 195 6m
Udut[L1]	2.892 732 8m	0.000 000 000 0	2.892 732 8m
Pdut[L1]	83.681 5u	0.000 000 000 0	83.681 5u
Z_mod[L1]	99.997 002m	0.000 000 000 0	99.997 002m
Z_phi[L1]	0.000 005 007 8	0.000 000 000 0	0.000 005 007 8
mjr[L1]	0.099 997 002	0.000 000 000 0	0.099 997 002

Figure 47: Example of TWM-LowZ algorithm results.

2.5 Open Z bridge tool

Although TWM tool itself can be used for occasional measurements of few discrete values of impedance, it is obviously not practical for frequent measuring of frequency dependencies with many spots. Thus TWM tool was from beginning developed with intention of automatic sequencing of the measurements. It would not be practical to implement such sequencer directly into the the TWM tool, due to many possible HW components and configurations that may exist, so it was decided to equip TWM with a simple API interface that enables controlling TWM from another application (the sequencer and source control). This API was developed after end of TracePQM project [10], so it was not documented at the time of release of the guide [1]. However, the API interface is available from 2019 and it was used to build a simple demonstration tool, the impedance bridge called “Open Z bridge”. The tool is open source project based on the LabVIEW 2020 environment and it is available at GitHub [5]. Basic features of the tool are following:

- Automated measurement of frequency, current level or DC bias current dependencies.
- Drivers for common measurement signal sources: Tektronix 3101C, Fluke 5000 series calibrators, DDS synthesizer based on cDAQ module NI 9260. Easily extendable for another instruments.
- Runtime display of readings and whole dependencies with uncertainties.
- Exporting of results to simple XLS reports.
- Indirectly usable to measure calibration data for calibration of the TWM measurement setup not only for purposes of Open Z bridge.

Figure 48: Main panel of Open Z bridge tool when measuring current level sweep.

2.5.1 Interfacing to TWM

Before any sequencer can be used, the TWM server API must be configured and enabled. It is initiated by clicking **Server** in the main panel of TWM which will invoke panel shown in Fig. 49. The API interface (server) is initiated by pressing **START** button. This will create named Windows pipe object of the name specified in the **Named Pipe Identifier**. Sequencer application (Open Z bridge) then uses this pipe to send commands and read responses from TWM. User can inspect the traffic by checking **Log traffic** and opening window **VIEW LOG**. Note the log should not run if not needed as it collects all data indefinitely. The TWM server panel must stay opened during server operation, so just minimize it but do not press **EXIT** or **STOP**.

Figure 49: Server panel of TWM tool.

2.5.2 Configuring bridge/digitizer

Configuration of the digitizing part of Open Z bridge comprises of two steps. First, user must configure TWM as described in chapter 2.4, i.e. setting up digitizers, transducers and corrections for given measurement setup. Also the TWM server operation must be enabled (see section 2.5.1).

Figure 50: Digitizer/bridge configuration of Open Z bridge tool.

Next step is to configure Open Z bridge itself. The configuration panel is invoked by clicking **Digitizer** in the main panel. The panel shown in Fig. 50 allows to choose either “dummy” mode, which is just a simulation for debugging purposes or “TWM client” which is the normal TWM control mode. First item to set is the **TWM pipe name**, which must match the TWM server window name set in the panel in section 2.5.1. Next, the TWM algorithm must be selected. The main algorithm for low impedances is “TWM-LowZ”. However, it is also possible to use “TWM-InpZ”, which is usable for rough measurement of

digitizer input impedance in process of calibrating the setup. Clicking the **REFRESH** will ask TWM to return parameters of the selected algorithm, which will be filled in the table or an error will be shown. The meaning of the parameters is identical as when directly set in the TWM tool in section 2.4.3. Do not setup parameter “f.est”, as it will be set automatically by the Open Z bridge itself. Control **Aperture override** allows to force TWM to set given aperture time to the digitizers when necessary, however default value is zero, which means TWM will set aperture time by itself following the digitizer configuration (typically following the table shown in Fig. 38). Next control **Discrete fs list** is used to limit the allowable sampling rates to certain discrete values. This is useful to limit number of required correction data sets for the digitizers otherwise Open Z bridge will choose any available sampling rate which may make corrections unusable. The discrete list function is enabled by checking **Limit fs to discrete list**. Next control is **Uncertainty calc. mode**. This must be set to something else then “None” to enable algorithm’s uncertainty calculation. Using option **Unc. for 1st reading only** will allow uncertainty calculation only for first reading per sweep spot, which may speedup data processing a bit. Note the “TWM-InpZ” algorithm has no uncertainty calculation implemented so it should be set to “None”. Button **Run ADC self-cal** will initiate TWM digitizers self-calibration routine. Note it may alter digitizer linearity, so use carefully, otherwise it may invalidate your tediously measured digitizer corrections e.g. for NI 5922!

The bottom part of the panel is used to control eventual DC bias voltage compensation unit, which is so far very experimental function following the idea presented in Fig. 19. Only the experimental prototype instrument “CMI LiBbias V1.0” is supported yet. Otherwise set the type to “Dummy”. When enabled, the Open Z bridge will try to iteratively adjust the DC bias compensator channels (up to three available) to reach zero value of TWM quantity name(s) given in the **Channel ? : quantity name**. So e.g. when the **Channel A : quantity name** is set to “Udc”, it will try to set channel A of the compensation unit to reach zero value of “Udc” quantity. The **Channel ? : initial voltage** is first iteration voltage of given channel. This is e.g. set to 4.2 V when measuring battery having nominal voltage of 4.2 V using digitizer with range ± 0.5 V. It will prevent the digitizer going into overload in the first iteration cycle. Leaving the **Channel ? : quantity name** empty will disable the channel operation. Unchecking the **Enable DC bias compensation** will disable the function for all channels.

2.5.3 Configuring source

Next step of setup is configuring the measurement signal source which is done by clicking **Source** in the main panel. The panel shown in Fig. 51 will be invoked. There are just four options and “Dummy” which will just simulate operation for debugging purposes.

Figure 51: Bridge source configuration of Open Z bridge tool when using universal arbitrary waveform generator.

2.5.3.1 Arbitrary waveform generators

The “Tektronix 3101C” and “Agilent 33120A” share the same setup in tab **AWG**. **VISA Address** of the instrument must be set here. Checking the **Generate DC bias** will allow the AWG to set DC offset of the generator in order to add DC current bias to the measurement signal when set in the measurement configuration panel. Checking **External reference clock** will enable phase lock of the AWG to external 10 MHz reference. Common setup for all source types is the **Amplifier gain constant [V/A]**, which defines transimpedance of the transconductance amplifier, which is expected to be used to amplify the AWG output. Do not mix up V/A with A/V coefficients here! It may lead to overloading the measured impedances. Rather start measurement with some very low current value unless you are sure here.

2.5.3.2 cDAQ DDS synthesizer

The next option is **cDAQ DDS**, which is a simple DDS function generator realized by cDAQ DAC converter NI 9260 (no other DAC devices are supported yet, but can be easily extended). The setup panel shown in Fig. 52 is invoked by pressing **CONFIG**. First control to setup is **DAC device address** which is location of the NI 9260 module in the chassis. Next, define output channel index which is done by **Channel indices**. So far only one channel is used by the Open Z bridge tool, so put just one number to the array. The indexing starts from zero and usually first channel is used, so use zero by default. The **DC offset [V]** numbers sets correction of the DAC+amplifier DC offset correction when needed. Enter one value per channel.

Figure 52: Bridge source configuration of Open Z bridge tool when using NI cDAQ DDS synthesizer.

Next step is to setup synchronization mode. As explained in section 2.3, the NI 9260 can either import timebase from NI 9238 or it can export its sample clock and provide it to digitizer HP 3458A. When importing clock from NI 9238, set the **Timebase mode** to “Take from ADC” and then select the NI 9238 module address **Reference clock device address**. Note the NI 9238 must already be active and running in the TWM tool as explained in section 2.4.1.2 otherwise it does not export its timebase clock to the chassis. The **Reference sample clock frequency [Hz]** is timebase clock frequency of selected source, which is 12.8 MHz for the NI 9238. In this mode of synchronization, the **DAC sampling rate [Sa/s]** must be set to 50 kSa/s, as internal clock of the NI 9260 is changed from its default 13.1072 MHz to 12.8 MHz. There is not much

sense to set lower values as it would only reduce the bandwidth. Other **Timebase mode** option is “Other source” in which case the timebase can be imported from specific source set by **Timebase source**. It can be imported e.g. from PF11 of the chassis. It is also necessary to set the **Reference sample clock frequency [Hz]**. The last option of **Timebase mode** is “Local”, which means to use internal timebase of NI 9260 module. The **DAC sampling rate [Sa/s]** must be set to 51.2kSa/s in the “local” mode. In any setup, the possible DAC sampling rates are defined by formula [12]:

$$f_s = \frac{f_{TB}}{D \cdot 256}, \quad D \in \{1, 2, \dots, 31\}, \quad (12)$$

where f_{TB} is timebase frequency and D is clock divisor integer.

The default values of **DAC buffer size [s]** and **Write block size [s]** are 1 s and 0.2 s. The first one defines total length of the round buffer of the DDS synthesizer, the latter one defines block size of the new waveform chunks written to the buffer. The latter values must be a fraction of the total buffer size to prevent underflow of the DDS, but not too small to not increase the update rate. Note first value 1.0 s means, any change in setup of DDS will appear with delay of up to 1 s, so the settling time in the measurement configuration must be set appropriately. Last experimental option for the DDS is **Dithering mode** and **Dithering level**, which allows to add defined noise to the synthesized sine wave before quantization. It may help to reduce DAC distortion at some conditions, however it is mostly useless in this particular application.

The regardless the master clock mode mode, it is possible to export sampling clock pulses using the **Sample clock destination** typically to **PF10** or **PF11** of the chassis or to the module with digital outputs. The function can be enabled by **Export sample clock**.

Figure 53: NI cDAQ DDS synthesizer test panel of Open Z bridge.

Validity of the setup can be checked by clicking **TEST**, which will invoke simple DDS test panel shown in Fig. 53. The panel will be closed with error message when the setup was invalid. Most likely cause is wrong setup of the sampling rate, or input reference clock, which can be determined by temporarily setting the **Timebase mode** to “Local”.

2.5.3.3 Fluke 5000 calibrators

Next possible source is any calibrator of the Fluke 5000 series. First control to setup is **VISA address** of the instrument. Next option is **Enable earthing** if supported by the calibrator. **External reference lock** enables phase lock to external 10 MHz signal, so it is available only for some of the models. Phase locking to low frequency signals e.g. for analogue calibrators Fluke 5720 is not supported. **Output mode** allows to select either “AC voltage” output which is then amplified by a standalone transconductance amplifier or “AC current” mode, which will output current directly. The **Amplifier gain constant [V/A]** in the source panel applies only for the “AC voltage” mode. The device can be tested by clicking ***IDN?**.

Figure 54: Bridge source configuration of Open Z bridge tool when using Fluke 5000 series calibrator.

2.5.4 Initiating new measurement

New measurement is configured and started by clicking **SETUP & START** in main panel. The panel shown in Fig. 55 will be displayed. First items to fill in are the **Source AC current** and **DC bias** which defines measurement level unless “Level” or “DC bias” sweep mode will be selected. Next, **ADC setup** rules must be set. **Min. fs [Hz]** defines minimum sampling rate for all measured sweep spots. **Min. fs/f₀ ratio** defines minimum allowed ratio of sampling rate to fundamental component, which is always higher than 2.0, however practically rather 2.5 or so (Nyquist–Shannon sampling theorem). **Sampling time [s]** and **Min. periods** define desired integration time (window length) per measurement. Checking **Coherent** will round the frequencies to nearest coherent sampling setup. Option **Periodic self-calibration** with time period set by **Self-cal interval [h]** allows to perform self-calibration/auto-calibration of TWM digitizers in specified intervals during the measurement. Note it may alter linearity for digitizers such as NI 5922, so this feature must be used carefully. It was intended for high precision measurements with HP 3458A where it may be needed to repeat auto-calibration every few hours for some several days long measurements (usually for linearization data measurement).

Figure 55: New measurement configuration in Open Z bridge tool.

Timing allows to set **Min. settling [s]** time after changing sweep spot. Settling can be defined also as number of periods of fundamental frequency by **Min. settling after level set [periods]**. Additional delay can

made before each reading by **Readout extra delay [s]**. Number of reading per sweep spot is defined by **Readings per spot**. Checking **Vari. count** will allow to set different readings count depending on AC current level. The actual counts will be generated with the list of sweep spots (see below). Particular sweep spots can be changed before all readings are done by setting up lower value to **Readings to change sweep spot**. The sequencer will make just this count of readings, then continues to next spot and eventually returns until full number of readings is done. **Averages** will let TWM do multiple internal records/readings per each Open Z bridge reading. **Sub-records** will set multiple sub-records in TWM, which may reduce effect of interference in the measured signals.

The next setup is generation of the measurement spots. The frequency and/or amplitude spots of the sweep are set in the left portion of the panel. There are several options. First, user must select type of sweep by **Mode**: “Frequency”, “Level” or “Bias” for DC bias current sweep. It is possible to fill in list of spots manually into the table on the left in which case it must be confirmed by clicking **Gen. custom**. Alternatively, it can be loaded with set of spots from a CSV file by clicking **LOAD** and the list can be also saved to CSV file by clicking **SAVE**. The tool will try to open any format of CSV regardless of separators, but default is one value per row and decimal dot as a separator. Another way is generating the list of sweep spots by parametric generator by clicking **Gen. sweep**. It is possible to select logarithmic or linear step by **Sweep mode**. The range and step must be defined. The values can be rounded by absolute and relative digits rules. Checking the **Skip mains freqs.** will try to avoid 50 Hz multiples to reduce mains interference. Checking **Random order** will perform sweep measurement in random order (the values in this panel will stay sorted). When generating frequency sweep, the current and DC bias are given by **Source AC current** and **DC bias**. When generating “Level” sweep, the frequency is constant given by **Single frequency [Hz]** control. It is also possible to check **multi-f. sweep** in which case **Gen. sweep** will open another panel where user can define multiple frequencies, so the “Level” sweep will be repeated for several frequencies. Single spot measurement must be confirmed by **Single spot** click. Clicking **Gen. sweep**, **Gen. custom** or **Single spot** will generate actual sampling setups which will be listed in the right part of the window. Always inspect parameters to verify all the levels and frequencies are set as expected. Empty list may be eventually caused by impossible set of **ADC setup** rules in combination with digitizer capabilities or discrete list of sampling rates in digitizer panel in Fig. 50.

The last step before confirmation is to set TWM measurement session folder by **Measurement(s) root folder** and measurement name by **Measurement root name**. Be cautious here to set valid path here as the Open Z bridge tool has to erase old results before new measurement. Although it erases only files and folders of expected names, it may accidentally erase something unwanted when the path is incorrect! Also preferably do not set the data path to SSD drive as the TWM will generate temporary measurement files for each reading. If HDD is not available, it may be good idea to use RAMDISK to save write cycles of SSD for frequent usage! Checking the **Add auto-incremented index** will generate different path for each reading, which may be useful to archive the data, but it will produce lot of files.

The measurement will be initiated by **OK**.

2.5.5 Viewing results

The results are shown runtime in the table **Sweep data** and in the graphs in the tabs on the right of the main panel. The display formats and quantities can be selected by the drop down menus below the table columns. The two rightmost columns can be switched to show either uncertainty in relative or absolute form (items “u(...)”) or absolute or relative deviation of the sweep spots from the first spot (items “d(...)”). The control **Select sweep spot** allow user to select either last measured spot (frequency and/or current) for the graphs in the **Z** tab or to select particular spot. The control **Phase index** selects measurement channel if there are more parallel measurements performer by TWM. Note it is titled “Phase” for compatibility with TWM power measurement naming convention. The tool can handle any number of channels (phases). This selector also affects the graphs. Next control **4TP display mode** is a switch to display of UUT shield impedance if the measurement is configured in “2x4T” connection according Fig. 21. Last control is **Uncertainty display mode**. User can select either just type A uncertainty “ua()”, or type A uncertainty expanded for level of confidence 95 % or combined expanded uncertainty for level of confidence of 95 %. Note the last option makes sense only if calculation of uncertainty is enabled in the configuration of bridge and corrections of digitizer and reference impedance contain valid uncertainties! This control also affects the graphs.

The tab **Z(f)** shows frequency or current sweep of the major and minor impedance components including

Figure 56: Left: FFT spectra viewer, right: Current sweep example of the Open Z bridge tool.

optional error bars (Fig. 56). The uncertainties are equal to the ones in the main table. The tab **FFT** contains copy of the FFT spectra of the reference and UUT channels same as can be viewed directly in TWM tool (Fig. 56). The last tab **Info** contains identifiers of the HW components of the setup.

Figure 57: Readings viewer/eraser of Open Z bridge tool.

Note sometimes the measurement procedure produces obvious outlier spot, which will be visible in the readings history in the graphs in **Z** tab. The Open Z bridge allows user to erase such spot from the data. It can be done by selecting the sweep spot where the outlier is, and using down menu of the results table (right click), selecting **Show readings** which will invoke panel shown in Fig. 57. Multiple rows of data

can be selected and removed by **DELETE**. The erasure can be performed even during measurement. The reading panel also enables to export the reading to XLS by right click to the table and selecting **Export — Export to XLS**. Format of exported numbers can be selected in the readings panel.

The results from the main table can be exported via the drop down menu (right click in the **Sweep data** table) and selecting **Export — Export to XLS**. Note the MS Excel must be installed in order to make this function work.

2.6 Setup calibration and Uncertainty of measurement

Uncertainty of the measurement using designed bridge comes mainly from following sources:

- **Coaxial network itself:** The errors caused by shunting impedances, potential drops in the cables, interferences between cables and components, etc.
- **Digitizer errors:** Interchannel transfer, linearity, crosstalk, etc.
- **Reference standard:** Calibration uncertainty of reference impedance.
- **Standard deviation** of repeated measurements.

Other sources, such as data processing algorithm inherent errors are in this case irrelevant as they are negligible compared to the four main sources.

2.6.1 Coaxial network contribution

Coaxial network uncertainty contribution was partially mentioned in the design of the topology. Possibly the only way of estimating contribution of the network itself is by modeling it in a circuit simulator such as Spice. This approach was taken and results presented in [6]. Example of circuit model is shown in Fig. 58. The components of the network were characterised in frequency domain and their parametric models were made, so a Monte Carlo simulation could have been performed with randomized parameter values.

Figure 58: Example of basic Spice model of 4TP sampling bridge used for validation and coaxial network uncertainty evaluation.

However, this simple approach could have provided only uncertainty contribution coming from shunting effects, loading effects and voltage drops in the network. The main concern is the effect of mutual coupling between the cables and ground lugs in the network. Their values are random depending on their mutual positions in the setup and the effects of the couplings depend on the level of current disbalance in the cables. It was not possible to generate all existing couplings in the network manually in the spice circuit as there are too many of them. Instead, a set of Matlab functions was made that generates all possible inductive and capacitive couplings between each pair of cables and ground lugs automatically. The used model of coupling for a coaxial cable is shown in Fig. 59. The coupling factors k_{STRAY} and C_{STRAY} were randomized during the Monte Carlo iterations together with the other model parameters. Using this process, an uncertainty of the network itself was estimated for particular digitizers and topologies. Eventually, the effect of crosstalk and linearity can be modeled this way. Results of a typical performance of 2x4T topology obtained by the Monte Carlo simulation is shown in Fig. 60. No significant difference was observed between the setups with NI 9238 and HP 3458A digitizers.

Figure 59: Spice modeling of stray coupling between cables and ground lugs. The upper portion of circuit is model of coaxial cable with coaxial choke having complex permeability. The lower portion is any number of self inductances of other cables and ground lugs.

Figure 60: Calculated expanded uncertainty of the 2x4T topology according for various Z_2 values for either NI9238 or Keysight 3458A digitizer ($Z_1 \approx 200 \text{ m}\Omega$). Note: not including digitizer linearity and reference standard calibration uncertainty.

2.6.2 Digitizer uncertainty contribution

Contribution of the digitizer uncertainty to the total uncertainty depends on corrections applied during the signal processing. The TWM tool enables plenty of optional corrections to be applied, which must be selected depending on the desired uncertainty of measurement (see TWM guide [1] for details).

The absolute minimum required for a reasonable operation of the bridge is to correct for the interchannel gain errors (frequency-amplitude independent) which are simple scalar corrections. It is not needed to calibrate absolute gains of the digitizer as it is just a ratio system. Similarly, an interchannel timeshift correction must be applied at least for the HP 3458A digitizers, because it reaches values around $1 \mu\text{s}$ in MASTER-SLAVE arrangement. However, this technique has a frequency limitation for both digitizer types. This approach will work up to few hundred hertz and it is reasonable to expect basic uncertainty no less than some $\pm 5 \mu\text{V/V}$ for HP 3458A and $\pm 15 \mu\text{V/V}$ for NI9238 even for optimal conditions, i.e. measuring of roughly equal voltage drops on Z_1 and Z_2 .

For frequencies above few hundred hertz, the individual frequency dependencies of gain and phase errors of each of the digitizer in the setup will cause diverging of their relative gain and phase errors with increasing frequency, so the basic uncertainty will grow by several orders of magnitude. Therefore, it is most desirable to perform at least frequency dependent gain and phase correction for single amplitude (TWM tool supports it as well). This should result in errors no greater than $50 \mu\text{V/V}$ and some $50 \mu\text{rad}$ at 5 kHz for both digitizers when measuring roughly the same voltage drops.

Above mentioned uncertainties apply for a case of roughly equal measured voltages drops at all digitizer channels, which is of course not likely condition. Otherwise, it is necessary to take into account amplitude dependence of gain and phase errors, i.e. linearity of the digitizers. Examples of measured amplitude linearities for HP 3458A are shown in Fig. 25 or Fig. 26. Note the phase error of digitizer is also

strongly dependent on the amplitude. Situation for HP 3458A gets a bit more complicated, because the shape of linearity also changes for various aperture times. The nonlinearity won't exceed some 10 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ even for low voltages when very slow sampling with aperture of 900 μs is used (frequencies up to some 300 Hz), as shown in Fig. 25. For faster sampling (aperture of 120 μs), it rises significantly as shown in Fig. 26. The shape and magnitude of nonlinearity is even worse for apertures below 100 μs which are needed for the frequencies above kilohertz. Situation with NI9238 is similar except the sampling frequency can be fixed at 50 kSa/s. Only advantage of NI9238 is more monotonic shape of its nonlinearity as shown in Fig. 26, which makes eventual linearity correction simpler. Two approaches can be taken here: (i) To measure the frequency-amplitude transfer for each frequency of interest and make frequency-amplitude correction for the TWM tool; (ii) To perform only frequency dependent correction for nominal amplitude and use estimate of the worst case nonlinearity as uncertainty of measurement. The first case (i) is quite tedious and time consuming process, however it may be performed once as the shape of nonlinearity should stay about the same at least for the HP 3458A because of its excellent stability and autocalibration feature. Long term linearity stability of the NI9238 is not yet known. In any case this approach leads to much lower uncertainties. The latter case (ii) is a fast approach for cases where uncertainties in order of 0.01% to 0.1% are acceptable.

Another source of digitizer uncertainty is aforementioned crosstalk. Crosstalk is dependent on more than just frequency and amplitude of the signal. It may also depend on common mode voltage or voltage difference between Low terminal and Guard due to the variable capacitive leakages. Therefore correcting for crosstalk in a setup with variable common modes mostly makes no sense. Therefore the only practical approach seems to be to measure its worst case value and use it as uncertainty contribution. Calculation of the absolute real and imaginary impedance uncertainty contribution for various topologies is following:

$$u_{\text{ct-4T}} = \frac{|Z_1|}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot 10^{ct/20}, \quad (13)$$

$$u_{\text{ct-4TP}} = 2 \cdot \frac{|Z_1|}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot 10^{ct/20}, \quad (14)$$

$$u_{\text{ct-2x4T}} = 2 \cdot \frac{|Z_1|}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot 10^{ct/20}, \quad (15)$$

where ct is negative crosstalk (e.g. -120 dB) and Z_1 is reference impedance. Note unless the crosstalk is higher than some 100 dB, its effect will be mostly masked by the coaxial network contribution itself and of course by the linearity of the digitizers.

2.6.3 Basic calibration via Open Z bridge

The Open Z bridge tool described in section 2.5 was designed for impedance measurement, however it can be effectively used for measurement of general complex voltage ratios when loaded with unity (dummy) corrections. Therefore it is useful tool for measuring calibration transfers (both amplitude and frequency dependent) for means of generating TWM correction data. It can be even used to measure data needed for linearity correction of the digitizer, although this is not topic of this guide. Following paragraphs will show how to configure and use the tool for means of generating correction data.

The most basic correction needed for operation of any AC ratio setup is correction of the interchannel transfer errors between particular digitizer channels. Following description shows basic interchannel transfer correction that does not take into account linearity, i.e. amplitude dependence of the absolute channel error. For convenience of use, the Open Z bridge tool can directly generate TWM correction files for this simple case.

First step is interconnection of all channels to be calibrated together to clean sine wave source (DDS generator) as shown in example in Fig. 61. Absolute gain error calibration is not needed for ratio system, so no reference voltmeter is needed. Note the connection would be the same for NI9238 channels. Different DDS to ADC synchronization connections are also possible as shown in section 2.3. The cables to the channels should be the same that will be used in the measurement setup so the digitizers are calibrated including cable errors.

Next step is to load TWM with neutral corrections. The digitizer corrections should be cleared in TWM corrections panel. Otherwise the measured transfer will be relative to the existing correction data. The transducer corrections in TWM must be loaded by "dummy" corrections (unity transfer -

Figure 61: Example of three HP 3458A digitizers connection for interchannel transfer calibration.

Figure 62: TWM transducer corrections assignment for interchannel transfer calibration for three channels.

no correction). Fig. 62 shows example of transducer configuration for calibration of setup with three digitizer channels. The digitizer “Channel #1” was chosen as a reference for all the remaining channels “Channel #2” and “Channel #3”. Therefore it was assigned with dummy current shunt correction for transducer #1 and #3. “Channel #2” and “Channel #3” were assigned as UUT, i.e. loaded with dummy voltage divider corrections in transducers #2 and #4. Transducer #1 and #2 share the same **phase index** of 1 and transducers #3 and #4 share the same **phase index** of 2. This configuration will result in two measurement results calculated by TWM, which will appear in Open Z bridge as two phases “L1” and “L2”, where result “L1” is relative transfer error of “Channel #2” from “Channel #1” and result “L2” is relative transfer error of “Channel #3” from “Channel #1”. There is no limitation on number of channels/phases, so the same procedure can be made with two digitizer channels, same as with e.g. four. It is just necessary to use the same digitizer “Channel #1” as reference for all pairs and increment **phase index** for eventual next channel pairs.

Next step is to configure Open Z bridge digitizer using **Digitizer** button as shown in Fig. 63. The equivalent connection “equ.cct” of the algorithm must be set to “Zphir” so the TWM will return $|Z|-\phi$, which is, in case of transfer calibration, a complex transfer between channels in polar form. “invert”

Figure 63: Example of digitizer configuration for measurement of interchannel transfer using Open Z bridge tool.

parameter of the algorithm must be disabled. The other options, such as the discrete list of sampling rates and aperture setup must be set in the same way as for the measurement so the calibration conditions are identical.

The measurement of the interchannel transfer(s) is setup and initiated same as ordinary measurement by clicking **SETUP & START**. The frequency range of calibration must be chosen to cover entire range of interest, however it is mostly not necessary to measure interchannel transfer below some 20 Hz. Both HP 3458A and NI9238 frequency transfers should be almost identical, so interchannel transfer should be flat below few tens of hertz. Number of calibration spots and their exact frequencies should be chosen with respect to shape of the transfer curve. The flat part (low frequencies) does not need to many spots, however the higher frequency part, where the transfer start deviate from unity should have finer step because TWM is able to interpolate the correction data to get correction for any frequency, but it may cause extra errors. Good strategy may be calibration at certain discrete list of spots and use only those for main measurements. **Source AC current** is equal to voltage in this function and it should be set to a level closest to level used for measurements of impedance itself.

Measurement itself is started by clicking **OK** in the New measurement configuration panel. Example of measured interchannel transfer for NI9238 module is shown in Fig. 64. The gain (quantity “Z [Ohm]”) should be always roughly flat up to few hundred of hertz and phase error (quantity “phir [rad]”) should grow linearly with frequency. This applies also for HP 3458A multimeters, although the phase error will grow much faster due to interchannel timeshift of approx. 1 μ s. At higher frequencies the digitizer channels will start deviating from each other mostly due to analogue front-end differences as is shown in the Fig. 64. The HP 3458A digitizers will deviate much more at frequencies above 1 kHz at shorter aperture times.

Next step is to use the measured transfer to generate the digitizer correction data. The correction generation panel is invoked via right-click pop-up menu of the result table **Sweep data** as shown in Fig. 64.

Figure 64: Example of measured interchannel transfer using Open Z bridge tool.

The panel shown in Fig. 65 should appear and the **Overview** should be filled with the measured data, one column per phase, e.g. two results for three digitizers from example setup above. There are just a few options to setup. First, the **Mode** allows to split the frequency dependence based on the aperture for HP 3458A or sampling rate for any digitizer. This point of splitting the frequency dependence is individual timeshift corrections will be generated for each aperture or sampling rate. This will reduce the residual phase shift correction to be applied by TWM. The checkbox **Use time shift** will enable timeshift correction of TWM, which will result in much lower phase shift corrections (recommended). **Use aperture correction** applies only for HP 3458A and it must be set to the same the same way as the frequency dependence was measures (enabled by default).

Figure 65: Digitizer correction generation panel in Open Z bridge.

The last option **Estimate non-linearity** is so far highly experimental and not properly validated. The purpose is to expand the frequency dependence by the amplitude dependent uncertainties covering worst

case digitizer linearity error, so the impedance algorithm will return worst case uncertainty estimate based on typical digitizer properties. This feature is currently in development and will be finalized when enough HP 3458A and NI9238 linearity data are collected.

Figure 66: Example of measured interchannel transfer after correction using Open Z bridge tool.

After setting up the correction parameters, the TWM digitizer correction can be generated by clicking **GENERATE**. File dialog will be opened allowing to create new or overwrite existing digitizer correction file. Open Z bridge will offer user assigning the new correction to TWM after the correction file generation. When the correction was generated and assigned to TWM, it is good practice to test if it was successful by remeasuring the frequency dependence again. Example of result of the test is shown in Fig. 66. The errors should be significantly reduced, however won't be zero due to limited stability of gain and phase of the channels.

Figure 67: Example of measured interchannel amplitude transfer after correction using Open Z bridge tool for NI9238 at 60 Hz and 50 kSa/s.

It is also possible to measure voltage dependence of interchannel errors at single frequency to get some idea of the difference between the channels as shown in example in Fig. 67. The example for NI 9238 modules in the figure shows the interchannel differences are below 0.001 % and few microradians, which is not terrible, however this is only the estimate of errors (uncertainty) when the impedance setup will measure nearly identical voltage drops on all its channels. It does not say anything about linearity (amplitude transfer) of the channels which is needed when measuring ratios other than 1:1. The Open Z bridge tool is currently not capable of linearity calibration.

2.6.4 Calibration of linearity

The calibration of linearity (amplitude transfer) of particular digitizers (channels) is out of scope of this guide as it is very tedious process, therefore it will be described only briefly. General idea is to somehow generate many known complex voltage ratios between two channels of the setup and evaluate ratio error of the channels pair. It is also necessary to repeat the process for multiple frequencies, as the linearity is frequency dependent. Some of the possible methods were described directly in TWM guide [1].

One of the traditional methods is use of precision inductive voltage divider (IVD) to generate known complex voltage ratios as shown in Fig. 68 on the left. Voltage \hat{U}_1 at the reference channel (MASTER) is held constant near full scale of the channel (e.g. 1 V), whereas ratio n of the IVD is gradually changed to produce various known voltages \hat{U}_2 for the calibrated channel (SLAVE). Thus errors of the second channel from expected output \hat{U}_2 of IVD can be calculated. Typical precision IVDs are single decade only, so the process covers only 100 % down to 10 % of the range. Thus it must be repeated several times while gradually reducing the voltage \hat{U}_1 at the reference channel and particular overlapping “chunks” of the amplitude transfer must be combined into amplitude transfer to cover entire used range of measured voltages. This process may not even produce usable data if the shape of the linearity is too erratic, which is typical problem below 10 % of full scale for HP 3458A. This process also calibrates only one channel, so the reference channel linearity may be obtained afterwards either by interchanging the two digitizers and repeating the whole process or by comparing all other channels in the setup to the one just calibrated by measuring the interchannel voltage transfer in connection showed in Fig. 65 as shown in Fig. 67. Apparently, use of IVDs is extremely tedious process when coverage more than some 10 % to 100 % of

Figure 68: Digitizer linearity calibration using IVD (left) or dual channel precision DDS (right).

the range at multiple frequencies is needed. The whole process cannot even be automated unless relay controlled IVDs are available. Furthermore, the whole process has one weakness. The interchannel gain and phase error of the two channels is not stable. Even HP 3458A may drift in order of 0.0001 % even at low frequencies and much more above 1 kHz. Other digitizers, such as NI 9238, will drift at least to order of 0.001 % and e.g. NI 5922 can drift up to 0.01 %. If the calibration process takes hours or even days, the results may not be even usable due to the drifts. Stability must be therefore analyzed prior linearity calibration to get estimate of achievable accuracy otherwise the whole tedious and lengthy process may be worthless. The problem of stability can be solved by using time multiplexing mode as shown in Fig. 69. The reference voltage \hat{U}_1 and variable voltage \hat{U}_2 are connected to multiplexer inputs and TWM tool will sequentially digitize these two voltages by switching the multiplexer. Therefore, this mode requires only one channel, however any number of channels may be calibrated simultaneously in parallel. Requirements for stability of the digitizers and multiplexer’s buffer is limited to period of multiplexing, which is typically

Figure 69: Example of connection of digitizers for linearity calibration using time multiplexing.

up to few seconds. Furthermore, the drifts can be further suppressed by alternation of the input switching order. Key component here is the multiplexer. Its inputs should be passive without buffers. Inserting buffers to input would insert further instability and another nonlinearity sources. Good solution is to use buffer only at the output of the multiplexer and substitution impedance networks at the multiplexer inputs that ensure constant input shunting impedance regardless of the selected multiplexer path. This concept of a multiplexer was used e.g. in [13]. Therefore, such multiplexer will have identical transfer at both inputs. However, the linearity of the output buffer is relevant as it becomes part of the calibrated linearity. The buffer must be either made using bootstrapping topology, which leads to extremely linear buffers (THD well below 140 dB) or it must be calibrated before. Fortunately, the buffer has unity transfer, so its amplitude transfer can be easily measured e.g. by another passive-input multiplexer setup connected between its input and output.

Another method is use of well characterised, dual channel DDS synthesizer to produce known complex voltage ratio as shown in Fig. 68 on the right. The process is similar to IVD, except the output voltage ratio can be set digitally and the whole process can be automated. Problem of this technique is that it is not possible to use most of the commercial DDS generators due to their very limited linearity and of course the DDS own linearity used must be calibrated prior usage, which is technically the same problem as for the digitizers. The DDS should only serve as a transfer standard.

One of the modern primary methods is to use quantum AC voltage sources PJVS or JAWS based on Josephson effect, however these are of course out of reach even for most national labs.

Another possibility is to obtain linearity of ratio setups by use of single fixed ratio device (e.g. 1:10 IVD) and use regression technique as was developed for digital sampling impedance bridge setup presented in [8]. The idea of the method is similar as calibration using IVD, except instead of holding reference voltage \hat{U}_1 constant and varying IVD's ratio \hat{n} , the ratio \hat{n} is held constant, e.g. 1:10, and the reference voltage \hat{U}_1 is varied with fine step over whole range of expected measured voltages. The obtained voltage dependence of ratio errors are then fitted by a model of nonlinearity using simple least square regression as shown in [8]. Model for the simpler case, where measurement is performed using time multiplexing (Fig. 69), is given by equations:

$$\hat{U}'_1 = \hat{U}_1 \left\{ 1 + g(|\hat{U}_1|) \right\}, \quad (16)$$

$$\hat{U}'_2 = \hat{U}_2 \left\{ 1 + g(|\hat{U}_2|) \right\}, \quad (17)$$

$$\hat{n} = \frac{\hat{U}'_1}{\hat{U}'_2} \left\{ 1 + g(|\hat{U}_1|) - g(|\hat{U}_2|) \right\}, \quad (18)$$

where \hat{U}'_1 and \hat{U}'_2 are applied voltages of known calibration device complex ratio \hat{n} , \hat{U}_1 and \hat{U}_2 are complex voltages measured by the digital sampling setup and function $g()$ is amplitude transfer (nonlinearity). Both inputs of the passive-inputs multiplexer share the same transfer $g()$, which simplifies the equations. Note in real conditions, the transfer $g()$ may be also dependent on phase shift between channels and

common mode voltage due to the crosstalk and shunting impedances, so these must be minimized by proper connection of the setup or digitally corrected. Nevertheless, this simple approach was successfully used to find amplitude transfers of many different setups with uncertainties even below 10^{-6} .

A bit more complex solution is required, when direct two channel measurement is used (Fig. 68). The two channels no longer share the same amplitude transfer, so one additional step is needed. The channels must be first connected together and their interchannel amplitude transfer $h()$ must be measured (Fig. 67):

$$h(|\hat{U}_x|) = g_2(|\hat{U}_x|) - g_1(|\hat{U}_x|), \quad (19)$$

where $g_1()$ and $g_2()$ are amplitude transfer of particular channels. The transfer $h()$ is then substituted into original equations:

$$\hat{U}'_1 = \hat{U}_1 \left\{ 1 + g_1(|\hat{U}_1|) \right\}, \quad (20)$$

$$\hat{U}'_2 = \hat{U}_2 \left\{ 1 + g_2(|\hat{U}_2|) \right\} = \hat{U}_2 \left\{ 1 + h(|\hat{U}_2|) + g_1(|\hat{U}_2|) \right\}, \quad (21)$$

$$\hat{n} = \frac{\hat{U}'_1}{\hat{U}'_2} \left\{ 1 + g_1(|\hat{U}_1|) - g_1(|\hat{U}_2|) - h(|\hat{U}_2|) \right\}, \quad (22)$$

The main advantage of this method is, it requires no operator input. It can run automatically over wide range of frequencies and amplitudes, although it may take even several days to collect enough data to reduce standard deviation of measurement at low voltages. Open Z bridge tool cannot directly be used to calculate the amplitude transfer, but it is usable to collect the input data as it can repeat measurement of voltage transfer for multiple frequencies in sequence, as shown in section 2.6.3.

2.6.5 Calibration of input impedance

Another correction item to calibrate for the impedance bridge operation is the input impedance of digitizers. In all the presented connections shown in Fig. 16 (4T), Fig. 19 (4TP) and Fig. 21 (2x4T) the input impedance of the digitizer and its cable will affect the measured impedance. In all the modes the input impedance of the reference digitizer and its cable is connected in parallel to the reference shunt, so its actual effective impedance value will drop. Typical HP 3458A with 1 meter input coaxial cable has typical input capacitance of $C_{IN} = 375$ pF and resistance well above 10 M Ω . If the reference impedance will be $R_{REF} = 600$ m Ω , we can expect error of measured phase angle:

$$\Delta\tau = R_{REF} \cdot C_{IN} = 225 \text{ ps}, \quad (23)$$

$$\Delta\phi = \Delta\tau \cdot \omega = 1.41 \text{ } \mu\text{rad/kHz}. \quad (24)$$

Although it is basically lower phase error than calibration uncertainty of most current shunts, it should be considered when the reference impedance is higher than e.g. 1 Ω . Same effect applies for the UUT impedance in 4T and 2x4T modes. Similar problem is in the 4TP mode, where the input impedance of the middle digitizer channel causes leakage of the current from the joint between the standards. TWM tool can correct both of these problems when input impedance of the digitizer channels is defined. The simplest way is to calibrate each digitizers' channel input admittance including the cable. See the TWM guide for details [1]. It shows methods to measure the input admittance as well as format of TWM digitizer correction. TWM tool with its integrated algorithm "TWM-InpZ" and one known impedance standard can be used to measure the admittance directly. Open Z bridge tool was extended, so it can use the algorithm "TWM-InpZ" as well, so the measurement can be performed via Open Z bridge in kind of automated way.

The procedure of using Open Z bridge to measure input impedance will be briefly described in following paragraphs. At least two channels are needed to perform the measurement. One is used as a reference and the other one is the UUT channel which input impedance is to be measured. First step is to calibrate interchannel gain and phase errors of the two digitizer channels as described in section 2.6.3. The correction must be loaded to TWM. Next step is to insert known impedance Z_{REF} in series with the analysed (UUT) channel as shown in Fig. 70. The value of the impedance should be comparable to expected input impedance of the digitizer. The accuracy of the measurement will be very poor if the value is e.g. 1 k Ω , whereas the input impedance modulus will be 10 M Ω . The reference channel's transducer in TWM transducer corrections must be set to dummy voltage divider with unity transfer and

Figure 70: Example of connection of digitizers for calibration of digitizer channel input impedance using TWM.

the UUT channel’s transducer must set to dummy shunt with unity ratio as shown in example in Fig. 71. Next step in Open Z bridge is to select the “TWM-InpZ” algorithm and fill in its parameters as shown

Figure 71: TWM transducers setup for measurement of digitizer’s input impedance. Channel 1 is reference, channel 2 is UUT.

in example in Fig. 72. The parameters are similar to “TWM-LowZ” algorithm. Preferred calculation mode is “WFFT” even for non-coherent sampling. Eventually, it is possible to use some window function. Desired output equivalent circuit is defined by parameter “equ”. Use “CpGp” if you would like to export the data as valid TWM input admittance correction. Last step is to define value of reference impedance Z_{REF} use for the calibration. For simplicity it is assumed to be frequency independent, so value measured close to the operating frequency should be used. The value is entered in Rp-Cp equivalent circuit. Both parameters must be filled even if it’s zero value.

Figure 72: Example of Open Z bridge configuration for measurement of digitizer’s channel input impedance.

2.6.6 Calibration timebase frequency

One remaining problem of the bridge measurements is accuracy of timebase. When synthesizer of the bridge is locked to external 10 MHz source with accuracy typically better than 10^{-6} , this correction will be more or less pointless. However, when using e.g. internal oscillator of NI 9260, which can deviate up to $\pm 0.01\%$, the measurement of reactance using resistive reference will result to up to $\pm 0.01\%$ errors. TWM and the impedance algorithm “TWM-LowZ” incorporate digitizer timebase correction to eliminate this problem. See TWM guide [1], section Digitizer correction - Timebase correction (optional).

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